

TANAUAN CITY COLLEGE

“Divergent Learning and Reflective Learning Styles of Selected Junior High School Students”

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to determine the distinction between divergent learning and reflective learning styles of the selected Junior High School students in Ulango Integrated School. Ulango Integrated School is located at 323 Rd, Ulango, Tanauan City, Batangas, which offers kindergarten to grade 10 primary educations. The respondents of the study were the selected junior high school at Ulango Integrated School enrolled in the Academic year 2023-2024, which was selected using stratified and random sampling with the total respondents of one hundred forty-five (145) consisting of thirty-three (33) grade 7 learners, thirty-eight (38) grade 8 learners, thirty-two (32) grade 9 learners, and forty-two (42) grade 10 learners. The result of the study can help the teachers and learners to identify suitable teaching strategies for the learning style of the students and encourage them to integrate them into their lesson plans and assessments. Through this, they can ensure that the learning gained by the students is valuable and can achieve the educational goals of the institution.

The researchers used a survey self-made questionnaire to assess the divergent learning style and reflective learning style of selected junior high school students at Ulango

Integrated School. This scale is used as the basis for the instrument for the data gathering of this research. The questionnaire was developed in two distinct sections by the researchers. The first part comprises ten (10) questions per domain that focus on divergent learning styles, and the second part explores the reflective learning style that also consists of ten (10) questions per domain with a total of sixty (60) questions. The researchers utilized mean, weighted mean, and T-test as statistical tools to analyze and interpret the gathered data about the perception and relationship between divergent learning and reflective learning styles.

Based on the study's findings, the researchers concluded that there was a significant difference between the Divergent Learning Style and Reflective Learning Style of selected junior high schools in Ulango Integrated School. Thus, it is recommended to conduct seminars/webinars, training programs, team building, sports, and joining different organizations on how to create or provide and promote a better learning environment and learning experiences that support their learners in practicing divergent and reflective learning styles.

In light of the conclusion derived from the study, it is recommended that school administrators provide seminars and training programs for their teachers and learners with the necessary tools and support for education to cater to catering different learning styles of the learners. Also, Team building, sports and joining different organizations or clubs can help both the learners and the teachers to build strong relationships and help identify the most suitable learning style and achieve expected outcomes. Future researchers can study learners' other and complex learning styles, other respondents, other levels, and the like to understand and innovate the way of teaching and learning based on the student's preferences.

Keywords: Learning Styles, Divergent, Reflective, Cognitive, Affective, Psychomotor, Domain

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The Researchers

DEDICATION

To the experiences we never expected,
financially challenged, the stressed
and troubled,
by God's kindness,
We managed to get through it,
We thank all for believing in and motivating us.

We dedicate this research study
to our friends, family, colleagues
and to the future researchers.

A.L.A
C.C.R.M
C.M.R.M
G.A

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Introduction

The educational process is a complex fabric where different learning styles and tactics converge rather than a standardized experience. The ability to examine concrete situations from various viewpoints sets Divergent apart. The divergent learning style is a learning style that has been proposed by David Kolb as part of his Experiential Learning Theory, among three other learning styles. Compared to convergent learning, divergent learning has the opposite learning capabilities. It prioritizes practical experience and reflective observation. Its most significant power is its ability to be imaginative and conscious of meaning and values. Although differences are a uniting force within a team, these types of learners are also very susceptible to peer criticism. Divergent learners stand, step back, observe, and contemplate the world, but always view things through the eyes of people. These learners are adept at assessing the surroundings, recognizing the individuality of every person and also highly perceptive to how the learners approach various people.

This learning style is linked to the concrete experience and reflective observation phases within Kolb's learning cycle. Divergent students can acquire information from these observations to effectively address challenges, make informed judgments, and acquire novel concepts. Divergent thinking is all about generating ideas that go beyond what is expected or usual. It is often referred to as thinking outside the box and is usually associated with creativity. Studies

suggest that our divergence capability is high and decreases as we become adults (Goodman, 2014).

Students who use divergent thinking can link ideas and approach challenges in novel ways. Divergent thinkers can solve difficulties in novel ways when it comes to education. Furthermore, divergent thinking fosters collaboration among students to produce original ideas. In addition to fostering teamwork, this prepares pupils for working in a college or professional environment. (Nelson-Danley, 2020). In divergent learning, one can think and have a creative mind, and it immediately has a good solution. Divergent thinking entails recovering prior knowledge and connecting disparate pieces of information in a fresh and meaningful way (Faust, 2018). Divergent learning facilitates enhanced cognitive processes by enabling individuals to gather and assimilate diverse knowledge, fostering independent thinking.

On the other hand, reflective learning is a highly personal activity rather than a social one. While educators in higher education have focused on developing learners' reflective competencies, there needs to be more research on the students understanding of reflective learning. The frameworks developed to facilitate our understanding of reflective learning are either purely theoretical or based mainly on the analysis of student learning artifacts. Reflective learning styles are all based on the experience of the learners. These learners are deep thinkers or thoughtful and might think about how to deliberate and analyze things.

Many individuals need more engagement in the learning process. Teachers and students actively participate in discourse, interact with the community, and collectively generate questions and answers in our educational setting. Moreover, learners exchange knowledge and effectively transmit it to one another. Reflective learning entails stepping back from a particular occurrence and engaging in a thoughtful examination of it, aiming to refine one's critical thinking abilities and enhance future performance. A more comprehensive assessment of student characteristics and requirements is necessary to enhance the evaluation process. (Tosuncuoglu, 2019). Upon reviewing the various research undertaken over the years, it was discovered that defining reflection was challenging.

The importance of separating reflection from other thoughts and ideas arises due to its abstract nature. In order to conduct such an evaluation, it is essential to establish a precise definition of reflection and appropriate criteria for assessment. Given the absence of a universally accepted description, various approaches have been employed to conceptualize this phenomenon. Some scholars adopt the notion of reflection, while others emphasize the significance of critical thinking or assessment. (Tosuncuoglu, 2019).

This process can be defined as reflection or reflective practice. Further, during this process, teachers employ various strategies to update their teaching styles; for example, correction strategies used by the teachers in the classrooms, how to improve students' positive attitudes toward learning English as a Foreign

Language, and how to improve their motivations (Han & Mahzoun, 2017; Han et al., 2016).

Engaging in reflective study can be likened to gazing into a mirror and honestly acknowledging the observations. Acknowledging one's accomplishments is essential, but it is equally imperative to identify areas for improvement to progress in the future. A reflective learner understands that failures are a common occurrence in the lives of individuals. Reflective learning is a highly advantageous talent that has the potential to enhance students' learning efficacy and facilitate the assimilation of novel experiences.

This study determines the significant difference between divergent learning and reflective learning styles of the selected Junior High School students. Moreover, researchers suggest that school administrators consider implementing targeted training programs, seminars, and educational workshops, which may include webinars to enrich the student's overall educational experience and foster a deeper understanding of the comparative research between divergent learning and reflective learning styles. Administrators can contribute to improving the learning environment in Ulango Integrated School's junior high school by offering opportunities for professional development of this nature.

Theoretical Framework

Kolb's learning theory mentions that individuals are inclined towards a specific learning style, which several factors, such as the social environment, educational experiences, and the fundamental cognitive structure of the individual, can influence. The divergent learning style is characterized by a preference for tasks involving idea production, such as brainstorming, in which individuals excel. Individuals with varying learning styles exhibit a propensity for diverse cultural pursuits and possess a proclivity for acquiring information.

Individuals with this learning style exhibit a keen interest in human beings and demonstrate notable proficiency in artistic endeavors. On the other hand, individuals with contrasting preferences tend to exhibit a propensity for engaging in collaborative endeavors, demonstrating receptiveness to diverse perspectives, and actively seeking personalized evaluations.

Reflective learning, on the other hand, entails engaging in critical thought regarding one's pre-existing notions. The process entails watching and evaluating the extent of information acquisition and understanding during the learning process. Furthermore, reflection enables learners to engage in a cognitive process wherein they may effectively analyze and make sense of the events that transpired during a particular experience. This process encompasses both recounting the experience and critically evaluating its many aspects.

The relevance of Kolb's learning theory to the present study lies in its focus on divergent and reflective learning, which prioritizes an individual's advancement through effective learning processes. By understanding these different learning styles and catering to them, educators can enhance their teaching methodologies and promote effective learning outcomes.

Conceptual Framework

To have a better presentation of the variables of this study, the researchers prepared a model of the foundation of the research expressed in the conceptual paradigm below. The figure below shows the input–process–output model suitable to the objectives of the researchers.

Figure 1: Research Paradigm

Figure 1 shows the paradigm of the study. It served as the flow of the research. The researchers used the Input-Process-Output model. The first box is named input. The input data needed in this study is the students' evaluation of the divergent learning style and reflective learning style. The second box is named the process. The process used to gather data is the use of research questionnaires prepared by the researchers. The last box is labeled as the output. The output of this study resulted in the formation of an enhancement program for students' divergent and reflective learning styles.

Objectives of the Study

The study sought to achieve its general objective by determining the distinction between divergent learning styles and reflective learning styles of selected Junior High School students, focusing on the following specific objectives:

- To determine the student's evaluation of the divergent learning style about cognitive, affective, and psychomotor aspects.
- To determine the student's evaluation of the reflective learning style about cognitive, affective, and psychomotor aspects.
- To identify if there is a significant distinction between divergent learning styles and reflective learning styles.
- To recommend work plans for junior high school to enhance the students' divergent and reflective learning styles.

Statement of the Problem

This study aimed to determine the distinction between divergent learning and reflective learning styles of the selected Junior High School students by exploring their distinction with one another.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the student's evaluation of the divergent learning style in terms of:
 - 1.1. cognitive;
 - 1.2. affective; and
 - 1.3. psychomotor?
2. What is the student's evaluation of the reflective learning style in terms of:
 - 2.1. cognitive;
 - 2.2. affective; and
 - 2.3. psychomotor?
3. Is there a significant difference between divergent learning styles and reflective learning styles?
4. Based on the study, what work plan can be proposed to enhance the students' divergent and reflective learning styles?

Hypothesis

- There was a significant difference between divergent learning and the reflective learning style of the selected Junior High School students.

Review of Related Literature and Studies

The study determined the divergent and reflective learning styles of selected junior high school students. It presents the situation and its variables through related study materials such as journals, articles, studies, and the Internet. All materials have provided the researcher with further understanding in establishing the framework and methodology for this study. The review includes learning styles, reflective learning, divergent learning, and domain of learning.

According to Vizeshfar et al. (2017), individual learners utilize diverse learning strategies, which are affected by their distinct personal attributes. The study highlighted the importance of recognizing the existence of varied learning styles and incorporating instructional approaches that cater to these styles. Further, this empowers educators to utilize suitable pedagogical methods proficiently. The researchers also found that divergent learning styles were prevalent among nursing students. Additionally, the study revealed that both students and lecturers expressed discontent with the existing education and teaching techniques.

Similarly, Alavi et al. (2017) emphasized that Teachers responsible for instructing diverse learners must acknowledge that each student may have a unique learning style when completing assignments and acquiring new knowledge. Therefore, educators need to be adequately equipped to cater to the various learning styles exhibited by their learners. Learning is a cognitive process involving the reception and assimilation of knowledge, which occurs universally among individuals. Indeed, the rate at which individuals acquire knowledge and make academic advancements must consistently align. Various aspects influence academic performance in the subsequent day. One of the aspects that can affect the learning process is the individual's learning style.

Moreover, Maya et al. (2021) stated that Universities strive to uphold the provision of high-quality education with a specific emphasis on fostering a diverse student population. According to the experiential learning theory, a variation in learning styles exists among learners. Within education, the teacher must possess a comprehensive understanding of the student, encompassing their cognitive abilities, which may be cultivated through training, and the attributes that influence their learning methods, including their emotions, thoughts, perceptions, and behaviors. Experiential learning theory posits that the learning process follows a cyclical or spiraling pattern, wherein the learner engages in activities involving feeling, reflecting, thinking, and doing. However, individuals exhibit varying

learning styles due to the unequal significance they assign to each component.

Based on the study of Shamsuddin et al. (2020),

Many higher education institutions are increasingly adopting blended learning (BL) as a pedagogical approach, providing a diverse range of programs that incorporate both online and in-class activities. The utilization of digital technology, including the Internet, email, notebooks, and cell phones, has significantly impacted many advancements in teaching and learning throughout most tertiary education institutions. Incorporating online resources in educational settings offers enhanced flexibility for involvement during learning. The extent to which universities and instructors have replaced face-to-face teaching modules with web content varies. There is no definitive guideline on the extent or specific components of a program that necessitates the utilization of web components. The primary objectives of education are to cultivate individuals who possess the necessary skills and knowledge to compete on a global scale effectively. Nevertheless, educators must possess a comprehensive understanding of the pedagogical approaches that can be employed inside the confines of the classroom, particularly in the context of current hybrid or blended learning methodologies. Before determining the teaching tactics to be employed in the classroom, it remains imperative to assess the learners' preferred learning styles.

In addition, Udhaya (2020) states that changes are seen in learners, their learning styles, and when they observe a sustained shift in behavior. Students learn in many kinds of methods at each level of the learning process. Difficulties arise in school due to differences in learning styles. It also emphasizes the vital role of learning style in determining an individual's accomplishment level and, consequently, their future career path. Students' ambitions and aspirations are defined mainly by the learning strategies they choose to use for learning. According to this study, teachers should evaluate each student's preferred learning style and modify their teaching strategies to suit that style best to accommodate learning preferences efficiently.

Along with Gudnason (2017), Learning styles-based instruction is prevalent in mainstream society and education, yet lacks empirical data to support its use. Limitations in learning-styles-based instruction are considered, and recent research in effective teaching practices is shared in this paper to provide evidence-based alternatives to learning-styles-based instruction. This study measures the student's learning styles, and it practice encouragement. It defines better learning style models when teaching methods match their learning style. It would be the combination of evolving the strategies of teaching skills that can be taught and recognizing the differences of the learners.

In addition, Hu et al. (2021) state that learning style, an essential component in a student's educational trajectory, has been a recurring subject in educational

and pedagogical discourse. The notion above, derived from psychology, psychological categorization, and cognitive research, is commonly characterized as an individual student's innate and distinctive approach to participating in educational endeavors. Learning styles provide valuable insights into students' cognitive processes, enabling the prediction of their academic achievements and playing a crucial role in the development of tailored instructional approaches. Identifying a student's preferred learning style and the subsequent adaptation of instructional methods to align with that style can enhance the student's pleasure, improve their academic achievement, and reduce the duration of the learning process. The significance of this idea is further emphasized when we consider divergent and reflective learning styles. Divergent learners, characterized by their inclination to investigate various perspectives and produce innovative ideas, and reflective learners, who excel in learning via thoughtful contemplation and analysis of the material, may exhibit discernible preferences regarding their learning styles. Educators can develop instructional strategies that accommodate these diverse learning styles by comprehending these preferences, thus enhancing student contentment and academic achievement.

Along with Chetty et al. (2019), Knowledge acquisition and cognitive processing are greatly influenced by the varied learning styles individuals exhibit. Unfortunately, there is sometimes a divergence between these learnings.

modalities and educators' pedagogical approaches, resulting in possible difficulties. Therefore, the importance of this study lies in its potential to improve education by enabling teachers to adapt their teaching methods to accommodate the unique learning preferences of pupils. Educators can optimize their instructional strategies by thoroughly comprehending the disparities between divergent and reflective learning styles, empowering them to proficiently customize their pedagogical approaches to address their students' specific needs. This effect has led to heightened student satisfaction and overall academic achievement.

Cid (2016) states that how individuals acquire and comprehend knowledge is significantly impacted by their learning styles, which encompass cognitive, emotional, and physiological attributes. Due to this factor, they play a crucial role in refining instructional methodologies and learning strategies for pupils. Furthermore, in conjunction with their research, the concept that individuals possess distinct learning styles serves as the fundamental basis for the notion of learning styles, which recognizes that individuals exhibit varying preferences for instructional methods. The procedures employed in information retrieval are not static but dynamic, adapting and evolving based on the nature of the sought-after information. The learning process is incomplete without distinct cognitive attributes, individual preferences, and inclinations. Each instructional approach is crucial in nurturing and augmenting these traits.

In addition, Gil et al. (2020) believed that student guidance, in its personal, academic, and professional dimensions, can be understood as the processes that promote an integral and individualized education for that person. As such, it becomes a proper field where the theory and practice of learning styles acquire its broadest meaning: a synonym for individuality, reaching its purpose with attention to the diversity of students in the classroom. This study examines student guidance and its acquisition of the learners' learning style. It is the individuality to reach the attention of the students. The students' knowledge helps to develop the learning process and the development of teaching. In addition, educational change processes the students' transitions in terms of their academic level.

According to the study of Dewi et al. (2018), Learning styles pertain to how individuals acquire and process knowledge. The findings of this study indicate that a significant proportion of students enrolled in arts, history, psychology, and literature departments prefer divergent learning styles. Acquiring divergent learning styles involves using imaginative capacity and a keen understanding of significance and worth. Further, this entails examining concrete scenarios from multiple vantage points and organizing various connections into coherent wholes. Lateral thinking, both productive and imaginative, facilitates the unhindered exploration of possibilities by granting emotions and intellect the freedom to operate. An awareness of meaning guides this process and values, commencing with an interactive educator who serves as a starting point. Therefore, individuals

with divergent learning preferences prefer engaging directly with information, observing, and comprehending it rather than being actively involved in applying the acquired knowledge.

Based on Palmiero (2020), Divergent thinking has been linked to various cognitive processes, such as intuitive and rational thinking styles. It involves finding many different and new responses or solutions to open-ended problems that value their importance to an individual's progress, especially in education. The study aimed to investigate the connections between decision-making styles and verbal and visual divergent thinking, as measured by the Torrance Test of Creative Thinking.

Mandela (2020) stated that Kolb's learning style proposed four different learning styles based on a four-stage learning cycle. Among the four learning styles, the divergent learning style is said to learn through interaction rather than content-driven learning. Additionally, divergent learners acquire knowledge by watching and feeling. Therefore, they favor hands-on activities that may be accomplished in pairs, groups, or as a team.

According to Bailie (2021), Reflective learning has been recognized for personal and professional growth, making it an essential learning experience in higher education. Despite potential advantages, there are different perspectives on what reflective learning entails and how it works. It is interesting to note that instructors have varying ideas about how reflective learning can enhance

professional practice, identity development, and the development of critical consciousness. Those who have a good understanding of reflective learning can provide support to students who prefer this type of learning or even encourage others to adopt it to benefit all students.

In addition, McCoy (2013) states that teachers effectively manage learning through the active engagement of all students through each class period. It demonstrates how students learn through active and reflective engagement with ideas, their surroundings, and other learners. It also asserts that involving students in integrative, thematic, and reflective learning activities could improve instruction in any cultural environment, anywhere in the globe. The benefits of using these tactics include higher engagement among students, which leads to more in-depth thinking and long-term retention of taught material.

According to Sugiarta (2023), it provides sufficient space for creativity and independence through talents, interests, and physical and psychological development. Further, this can be achieved by applying the suitable learning model, which is a factor that influences from the outside while still paying attention to psychological factors that come from within. Strong knowledge of students, develop students thinking skills and the social aspects. It emphasizes the learning process in class and balances the harmonious manner of the generative learning model. This study aims to analyze reflective learning and to know the individual's unique abilities.

Furthermore, Tan (2021) states that there are differences in the quality of student reflection. When students are asked to reflect, it is often assumed that they know how to do it automatically. As long as students struggle with critical reflection and the act of reflection itself, further study is needed to understand how students view reflection and the difficulties they face. It also highlights the need for a deeper comprehension of students' perspectives, as students frequently saw reflection as a single-layered (non-iterative) and monologic product instead of an iterative and dialogic process. The analysis provides insights that point to the need for a deeper understanding and contextual awareness of the student perspective to design better instruction that supports and strengthens a reflective learning approach.

In accordance with Hwang et al. (2019), situated learning asserts that learning happens in social contexts and knowledge advances from engagement in a social community. Thus, teachers must create a social situation facilitating students' engagement in the learning activity. It describes knowledge in authentic content. It enhances their learning environment—lack of practical support and concrete learning activities. Additionally, the students with higher self-efficacy can be more engaged in thinking and reflecting.

According to Chan (2021), Experiences alone do not always result in learning; active and conscious reflection of one's experiences, emotions, actions, and responses is crucial. *Reflection* is a pedagogical approach essential to experiential learning and is a crucial component of Kolb's Learning Cycle, in which

knowledge is formed from transforming experience. Moreover, many names for reflection are frequently used in literature, such as reflective thinking, self-reflection, and reflective process. At this point, there is no agreement on a phrase preferable for reflection.

In addition, Wain (2017) the role of reflection as a learning tool derived from everyday experiences is crucial in midwifery programs at the undergraduate and postgraduate levels. It encourages students to utilize a systematic model of reflection to illustrate their ability to introspect on their clinical practice experiences. It also underscores the value of reflection in ongoing professional advancement and revalidation. Furthermore, it explores how reflection aids midwives in becoming reflective practitioners, thereby fostering self-awareness, self-identity, and personal development.

According to the study of Hoque (2016), learning can be experienced anywhere, meaning we can acquire or gain knowledge everywhere. In addition, there are three domains of learning: cognitive, affective, and psychomotor. Within each domain are multiple levels of learning that progress from more basic, surface-level education to more complex, deeper-level learning.

Synthesis

The research conducted by Vizeshtar, Shamsuddin, Cid, Chan, and Dewi focuses on identifying the most suitable pedagogical technique for accommodating students' individual learning preferences. The study primarily centers around the contrasting learning styles exhibited by students in higher education, with Chan's study explicitly highlighting the significance of reflective learning styles. The researchers aim to identify the most effective teaching methods to cater to the diverse learning styles of students and enhance their learning outcomes.

On the other hand, the research conducted by Bailie, Wain, and Tan focuses on the instructor's comprehension of reflective learning and their strategies for assisting students who prefer this learning approach. The study emphasizes the need for efficient methods to enhance reflective learning methodologies within educational settings. The researchers aim to explore the techniques used by instructors to promote reflective learning and the effectiveness of these strategies in enhancing students' learning outcomes.

Both studies highlight the importance of understanding individual learning preferences and the need to cater to these preferences for effective learning outcomes. The research findings can help educators design effective pedagogical strategies that promote student-centered learning and enhance their educational experience.

Research Design

In this study, the researchers utilized the causal-comparative quantitative research design to test the comparison between the input data of this research to come up with the output of the study.

A causal-comparative quantitative design was the research design used for this study because the researchers sought to see if there was a significant difference between students' evaluation of divergent learning styles and reflective learning styles. The researchers did not manipulate any variables; they only investigated the differences between students' evaluation of divergent learning styles and reflective learning styles. Obviously, since other factors exist, the causal-comparative research design has been reviewed to see how different elements were controlled.

Sampling

The focus of this study were the student population of a junior high school comprising 227 students who are equally selected throughout four grade levels: 7th, 8th, 9th, and 10th. To obtain a sample that accurately represents the population, the researchers utilized stratified random sampling method.

Stratified random sampling is a probability sampling method that involves dividing the target population's elements into distinct groups or strata. Within each stratum, the elements are similar concerning select characteristics of importance

to the survey (Parsons, 2023). This method helps ensure that the sample accurately represents the population's diversity and characteristics. Moreover, this method ensures that all members of the population have an equal chance of being chosen, regardless of any characteristics, such as their grade level (Frost, 2023). This method tends to produce representative, unbiased samples, which means that all the students within the junior high school at Ulango Integrated School have an equal opportunity to be chosen in this study.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents of the study were the selected students at Junior High School in Ulango Integrated School enrolled in the academic year 2023-2024. The researchers used stratified random sampling to select the respondents for this study, which were the selected Junior High School students of Ulango Integrated School. The researchers utilized the Taro Yamane formula to find the exact number of respondents from the population of senior high school students at Ulango Integrated School. Table A shows the total number of respondents.

Table A
Respondents of the Study

Grade Level	Total Population	Sample Size	Percentage
Grade 7	53	33	23%
Grade 8	59	38	26%
Grade 9	49	32	22%
Grade 10	66	42	29%
Total	227	145	100%

Research Instrument

The researchers used a survey self-made questionnaire to assess the divergent and reflective learning styles among a sample of junior high school students at Ulango Integrated School. This scale was used as the basis for the instrument for the data gathering. The questionnaire was developed in two distinct sections by the researchers.

The research instrument consisted of two parts, with the first part comprising ten (10) questions focused on divergent learning styles. The second part of the instrument explored the reflective learning style. In order to gather data, the chosen junior high school evaluated the items by assigning ratings on a 4-point scale, indicating the extent to which each item is applicable. The participants' responses were categorized into four levels of agreement: "Strongly

Agree" (rated as 4), "Agree" (rated as 3), "Disagree" (rated as 2), and "Strongly Disagree" (rated as 1). The researchers utilized the mean ranges and their corresponding interpretations to describe the computed weighted mean and average weighted mean. Table B presents the Numerical Value, Mean Ranges and corresponding Interpretations.

Table B
Interpretation of Mean Ranges

Numerical Value	Mean Range	Interpretations
4	4.00 - 3.25	Strongly Agree
3	3.24 - 2.50	Agree
2	2.49 - 1.75	Disagree
1	1.74 - 1.00	Strongly Disagree

Validity and Reliability

Research instrument was implemented to assess the study's validity and reliability. The initial version of the questionnaire was submitted to the thesis adviser for feedback, input, and revisions. Three validators validated the questionnaire.

To establish the validity and reliability of the research instrument, the statistician recommended applying Cronbach's alpha for reliability and Pearson's r-moment correlation for the validity test.

The researchers used Cronbach's alpha to test a research instrument's reliability. Cronbach's alpha is a statistical method that measures the internal consistency of a scale or instrument. It assesses the degree to which a set of items in the hierarchy or tool measures the same underlying construct. Researchers used Cronbach's alpha to ensure their instruments are reliable and produce consistent results. Reliability is crucial for drawing accurate conclusions and making valid recommendations based on the collected data.

On the other hand, to test the validity of the questions in a research instrument, Pearson's r-moment correlation is used. Pearson's r is a statistical method that measures the degree of association between two variables, indicating how strongly they are related. In the context of a research instrument, the researchers used Pearson's r to assess whether the questions are measuring what needs to be measured and whether they are meaningfully related to each other. Using Pearson's r-moment correlation, the researchers can ensure that their research instrument has good validity, providing confidence that the data collected measures the intended concepts. In addition, to test the content validity of the research instrument, it was validated by the panel of experts.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researchers utilized a self-made questionnaire to determine the respondents' evaluation of divergent learning and reflective learning styles. Additionally, the survey consisted of closed-ended questions specially designed to collect quantitative data. The questionnaire was divided into two separate parts. One cohort emphasized divergent learning styles, while the other promoted a reflective one. In collecting the data, the researchers forwarded a letter to the school's principal and advisers, followed by the parents of the students, for permission to conduct the study.

Afterward, the researchers distributed the survey questionnaire to the selected Junior High School students at Ulango Integrated School. The researchers used descriptive and inferential statistics to determine the perception and relationship between divergent learning and reflective learning styles. The results were treated with the utmost confidentiality.

Ethical Consideration

It was crucial to ensure the privacy and security of the participants in this study, given that it involved collecting their personal information. To achieve this, the researchers made sure to relay all the essential details of the study, including its objectives, to the participants to help secure their consent and confidentiality. By doing this, the respondents understood their role in the research and were more

willing to participate. Additionally, the researchers maintained the confidentiality of the respondents by not disclosing their names or any other identifying information. Ethical consideration helped to protect their privacy and ensure that their personal information was not misused.

Treatment of Quantitative Data

To satisfy the requirements of the research, the researchers made use of appropriate statistical treatment. The gathered data undergone the statistical treatment outlined below.

Statement of Problems 1 and 2: Since the study used a causal-comparative quantitative research design, the researchers used descriptive statistics with the approval of the statistician. Descriptive statistics are summary statistics that quantitatively describe or summarize features from a collection of information, while descriptive statistics is the process of using and analyzing those statistics. The researchers employed the weighted mean formula to gauge students' evaluation of the divergent learning styles and reflective learning styles.

Formula:

$$\text{Weighted Mean} = \frac{\sum x}{N}$$

N

Where x = level of
preference

N = the no. of learners

$$\text{Weighted Mean} = \frac{fx_1 + fx_2 + \dots + fx_n}{f_1 + f_2 + \dots + f_n}$$

Where;

X = level of preference

F = the frequency

Statement of Problem 3: To test the significant differences between the students' evaluation of divergent learning styles and reflective learning styles, researchers used the Paired T-test formula:

$$t = \frac{\sum d}{\sqrt{\frac{n(\sum d^2) - (\sum d)^2}{n-1}}}$$

Where $\sum d$ is the sum of the differences.

The researchers utilized the Taro Yamane formula to find the exact number of respondents from the population.

Yamane Formula:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Presentation, Analysis, and Interpretation of Data

1. Students' evaluation of the Divergent learning style.

The following section presents the students' evaluation of learners with divergent learning styles

1.1 Cognitive

In terms of cognitive, the indicators were explored. The table below indicates the **students' evaluation of the divergent learning styles** of the respondents in terms of cognitive. Table 1.1 shows the results of the conducted.

Table 1.1

Students' Evaluation of the Divergent Learning Style in terms of Cognitive.

Indicators	M	SD	VI
As a student, I...			
1. am naturally inclined to generate multiple ideas, even if they seem unconventional or impractical.	3.12	0.71	Agree
2. am consciously evaluate multiple alternatives and select the most appropriate one after careful consideration.	3.17	0.73	Agree
3. am open to considering new ideas and perspectives, even if they challenge my existing beliefs.	3.26	0.70	Strongly agree
4. find myself seeking out diverse viewpoints to enrich my understanding and problem-solving abilities.	3.14	0.76	Agree
5. suggest multiple solutions to problems, considering both conventional and unconventional approaches.	3.28	0.68	Strongly Agree
6. am comfortable with ambiguity and uncertainty, embracing the open-ended nature of creative thinking.	3.14	0.77	Agree
7. find it exciting to generate innovative ideas and explore uncharted territories in my thinking.	3.12	0.77	Agree
8. usually question the ways of thinking to come up with new and creative ideas.	3.19	0.71	Agree
9. extend the power of divergent thinking in generating novel solutions and fostering creativity.	3.14	0.71	Agree
10. am committed to develop my divergent thinking skills to enhance my problem-solving and innovative potential.	3.31	0.70	Strongly Agree
GENERAL WEIGHTED MEAN	3.19	0.03	Agree

M-(mean), *VI*-(verbal interpretation), *SD*-(standard deviation), 4.00-3.25- (strongly agree), 3.24-2.50- (agree), 2.49-1.75
 1-(disagree), 1.74-1.00- (strongly disagree)

Table 1.1 presents the indicators of the student evaluation of the learners regarding the divergent learning styles in terms of cognitive. The respondents Strongly Agree that *they are committed to developing their divergent thinking skills to enhance their problem-solving and innovative potential*, which obtained the highest mean of **3.31** with a standard deviation of 0.70 and that *they can suggest multiple solutions to problems, considering both conventional and unconventional approaches* with a mean of **3.28** and standard deviation of 0.68.

Moreover, the respondents also Agree that *they can find it exciting to generate innovative ideas and explore uncharted territories in their thinking* with a mean of **3.12** and standard deviation of 0.77, also that *they are naturally inclined to generate multiple ideas, even if they seem unconventional or impractical* with a mean of **3.12** and standard deviation of 0.71.

Overall, based on the result of Table 1.1, it is seen that most of the respondents agree that using divergent learning style can be beneficial in terms of cognitive factors such as enhancing their problem-solving, innovative potential, and it helps in creating suggestions for multiple solutions to problems, considering both conventional and unconventional approaches. In addition, it also encourages learners to generate innovative ideas and explore uncharted territories in their thinking.

According to Dewi, D. K., & Tandyonomanu, D. (2018) Entitled "Convergence vs. Divergence Learning Style Study of Critical Thinking. "The

survey revealed that many students pursuing arts, history, and literature prefer divergent learning styles. Additionally, it was mentioned that those with divergent learning styles prefer immediately engaging with information, observing it, and comprehending it rather than actively applying the knowledge the learners have received. It emphasizes the significance of incorporating divergent learning styles into learners' cognitive processes. The findings of Dewi, D. K., & Tandyonomanu, D. (2018) are consistent with the results of Table 1.1, which suggest that divergent learning styles can be an effective strategy for enhancing learners' cognitive processes, especially in problem-solving and generating multiple ideas that lead them to generate multiple ideas unconventionally and evaluate it to select the most appropriate solutions. It makes the learners more creative in forming a novel solution by seeking out diverse viewpoints to enrich their understanding.

1.2 Affective

In terms of affective, the indicators were explored. The table in the next page indicates the **students' evaluation of the divergent learning styles** of the respondents in terms of affective. Table 1.2 shows the results of the conducted survey.

Table 1.2

Students' Evaluation of the Divergent Learning Style in terms of Affective.

Indicators	M	SD	VI
As a student, I...			
1. feel energized and excited when I am encouraged to generate multiple ideas and explore different possibilities.	3.32	0.69	Strongly Agree
2. find immense satisfaction in participating in brainstorming sessions where I feel free to express my unique ideas, not having any burden by the fear of criticism or judgment.	3.26	0.63	Strongly Agree
3. feel a sense of accomplishment when I come up with innovative solutions or unconventional approaches to problems.	3.30	0.66	Strongly Agree
4. find myself developing a more positive attitude towards risk-taking and embracing uncertainty in the learning process.	3.33	0.76	Strongly Agree
5. appreciate the opportunity to collaborate with others as I can conceptualize the connection from different perspectives.	3.21	0.68	Agree
6. feel a sense of belongingness when I participate in divergent thinking activities in the classroom.	3.20	0.71	Agree
7. am more likely to engage with the learning material when I am encouraged to explore different perspectives and approaches.	3.28	0.67	Strongly Agree
8. find myself developing a stronger sense of creativity and innovation as I engage in divergent thinking activities.	3.26	0.67	Strongly Agree
9. appreciate the value of divergent thinking in fostering open-mindedness and adaptability to change.	3.28	0.68	Strongly Agree
10. am committed to develop my divergent thinking skills to enhance my problem-solving and creative potential.	3.32	0.67	Agree
General Weighted Mean	3.27	0.03	Strongly Agree

M-(mean), VI-(verbal interpretation), SD-(standard deviation), 4.00-3.25- (strongly agree), 3.24-2.50- (agree), 2.49-1.75- (disagree), 1.74-1.00- (strongly disagree)

Table 1.2 presents the indicators of the students' evaluation of the divergent learning style in terms of affective. Based on the result, the learners strongly agree that *they are developing a more positive attitude towards risk-taking and embracing uncertainty in the learning process*, which obtained the highest mean of **3.33** and standard deviation of 0.69, and that *they feel energized and excited when they are encouraged to generate multiple ideas and explore different*

possibilities with a mean of **3.32** and standard deviation of 0.67. The respondents also agree that *they appreciate the opportunity to collaborate with others as they can conceptualize the connection from different perspectives, and they are committed to developing their divergent thinking skills to enhance their problem-solving and creative potential*, with a mean of **3.21** and a standard deviation of 0.68. Furthermore, *they also feel a sense of belongingness when they participate in divergent thinking activities in the classroom*, with a mean of **3.20** and a standard deviation of 0.71.

Overall, Based on the result of Table 1.2, it appears that most of the respondents strongly agree that using divergent learning style can be beneficial in terms of affective factors such as developing a more positive attitude in risk-taking and embracing uncertainty, feeling energized and excited when encouraged to generate multiple ideas and explore a different perspective, committed to enhancing their problem-solving and creative potential, appreciate the opportunity to collaborate with others and feel a sense of belongingness when participating in divergent thinking activities in the classroom.

Based on Mandela (2020), students who use divergent learning styles are warm, outgoing, concrete thinkers, expressive, spontaneous, and group-oriented, which affects their feelings and emotions as the students like people and listen to others with an open mind. Furthermore, students learn more through interactions and hands-on projects that can be completed in group work, pairs, or teams. The

findings of Mandela (2020) support the results of the study presented in Table 1.2, which suggests that the learners benefit from using divergent learning styles, including their attitude and motivation towards connecting with other students and uncertainty in their learning process. These help the learners to have a positive learning environment that will allow them to participate and use their creativity and uniqueness in collaborative activities.

1.3 Psychomotor

In terms of psychomotor, the indicators were explored. The table below indicates the **students' evaluation of the divergent learning style** in terms of psychomotor. Table 1.3 shows the results of the conducted survey.

Table 1.3
Students' Evaluation of the Divergent Learning Style in terms of
Psychomotor

Indicators	M	SD	<u>VI</u>
As a student, I...			
1. am able to generate multiple strategies and approaches to solving physical tasks.	3.32	0.67	Strongly Agree
2. try new things and experiment with different materials and techniques during hands-on activities.	3.33	0.71	Strongly Agree
3. participate in hands-on activities, and this challenged me to think outside the box.	3.24	0.66	Agree
4. can effectively express my ideas creatively through writing, drawing, or other mediums.	3.20	0.76	Agree
5. can collaborate with others using physical means to generate and develop creative ideas.	3.47	0.66	Agree
6. like to practice until I can do things smoothly and consistently.	3.32	0.72	Strongly Agree
7. enjoy refining my skills and achieving perfect control.	3.34	0.68	Strongly Agree
8. can create something entirely new and original.	3.22	0.76	Agree
9. learn by watching and imitating exactly what is being demonstrated.	3.20	0.75	Agree
10. can review in different ways, such as by creating flashcards, doing peer study, and creating scenarios.	3.30	0.72	Agree
General Weighted Mean	3.29	0.35	Strongly Agree

M-(mean), *VI*-(verbal interpretation), *SD*-(standard deviation), 4.00-3.25- (strongly agree), 3.24-2.50- (agree), 2.49-1.75 -(disagree), 1.74-1.00- (strongly disagree)

Table 1.3 presents the indicators of the students' evaluation of the divergent learning style in terms of Psychomotor. The respondents stated, based on the result, Strongly Agree that *they can collaborate with others using physical means to generate and develop creative ideas*, which obtained the highest mean of **3.47** with a standard deviation of 2.7, and that *they enjoy refining their skills and achieving perfect control* with a mean of **3.34** with a standard deviation of .68.

Moreover, the respondents also Agree that *they can create something entirely new and original* with the least mean of **3.22** with a standard deviation of .76. and that *they can effectively express their ideas creatively through writing, drawing, or other mediums. They learn by watching and imitating precisely what is being demonstrated* with the same mean of **3.20** with a standard deviation of .76 and .75.

Overall, based on the result of Table 1.3, it is seen that most of the respondents strongly agree that using divergent learning style can be beneficial in terms of psychomotor factors such as collaborating with others using physical means to generate and develop creative ideas, enjoying refining their skills and achieving perfect control, reviewing in different ways, such as creating something entirely new and original, effectively expressing their ideas creatively through writing, drawing, or other mediums, and learning by watching and imitating precisely what is being demonstrated.

According to Vizeshfar et al. (2017) found that practical and engaging teaching methods enhance student learning experiences by incorporating interactive and hands-on approaches; students are more likely to grasp concepts effectively, stay motivated, and develop a deeper understanding of the subject matter. The study also found that practical activities play a crucial role in enhancing learning at universities, replacing outdated approaches with innovative methods to improve student learning outcomes.

Overall, the findings of Vizeshfar et al. (2017) support the results of the study presented in Table 1.3, which suggest that by promoting interactivity and hands-on experiences, educators can create a more engaging and effective learning environment for learners. In addition, Learners with divergent learning styles tend to excel in generating multiple strategies for problem-solving, experimenting with various materials and techniques, and expressing creativity through writing, drawing, or collaboration. These learners enjoy refining their skills, achieving mastery, and learning through observation and imitation. Additionally, divergent learners are adept at reviewing information in diverse ways, such as creating flashcards or engaging in peer study.

2. Students' evaluation of the reflective learning style

The following section presents the students' evaluation of the reflective learning style

2.1 Cognitive

In terms of cognitive, the indicators were explored. The table below indicates the **students' evaluation of the reflective learning style** of the respondents in terms of cognitive. Table 2.1 shows the results of the conducted survey.

Table 2.1
Students' Evaluation of the Reflective Learning Style in terms of Cognitive.

Indicators	M	SD	VI
As a student, I...			
1. often think about how new information is somewhat connected to what I already know.	3.13	.59	Agree
2. find myself analyzing information carefully to ensure I thoroughly grasp it.	3.23	.70	Agree
3. regularly evaluate the pros and cons of different ideas before making a decision.	3.14	.80	Agree
4. am inclined to reflect on my learning experiences to gain deeper insights.	3.08	.70	Agree
5. connect new information to my personal experiences and beliefs to enhance understanding.	3.28	.68	Strongly Agree
6. am drawn to consider the implications of new information in real-world scenarios.	3.03	.74	Agree
7. find myself questioning assumptions and seeking multiple perspectives to gain a comprehensive understanding.	3.09	.70	Agree
8. am inclined to revisit and revise my understanding of concepts based on new information and reflections.	3.10	.70	Agree
9. understand the process of self-reflection to enhance my learning and personal growth.	3.24	.70	Agree
10. am committed to continuous learning and seeking opportunities to broaden my knowledge and understanding.	3.25	.72	Strongly Agree
GENERAL WEIGHTED MEAN	3.16	.05	Agree

M-(mean), *VI*-(verbal interpretation), *SD*-(standard deviation), 4.00-3.25- (strongly agree), 3.24-2.50- (agree), 2.49-1.75 -(disagree), 1.74-1.00- (strongly disagree)

Table 2.1 presents the indicators of the student's evaluation of the reflective learning style. The respondents strongly Agree that *they can connect new information to their personal experiences and beliefs to enhance understanding*, which obtained the highest mean of **3.28** with a standard deviation of 0.68, and that *they are committed to continuous learning and seeking opportunities to broaden their knowledge and understanding* with a mean of **3.25** and a standard deviation of 0.72.

Moreover, the respondents also Agree that *they understand the process of self-reflection to enhance their learning and personal growth* with a weighted mean of **3.24** and standard deviation of 0.70 also that *they can find themselves analyzing information carefully to ensure they thoroughly grasp it* with a mean of **3.23** and standard deviation of 0.70.

Based on the result of Table 2.1, most of the respondents agree that using reflective learning style can be beneficial in terms of cognitive factors such as personal growth, self-reflection, connecting new information to their personal experiences and beliefs which help to enhance their understanding, and analyzing information carefully to ensure the learners thoroughly grasp it.

These findings align with the study conducted by Tan (2021), which explains that when required to reflect, students would be made more cognisant of their thinking and thoughts and, as a result, would participate more actively, pay more

attention, Moreover, put in more effort. It also highlights the need for a deeper comprehension of students' perspectives, as students frequently saw reflection as a single-layered (non-iterative) and monologic product instead of an iterative and dialogic process.

Overall, the findings of Tan (2021) support the results of the study presented in Table 2.1 which indicate that adopting a reflective learning style can be a valuable approach to improving learners' cognitive processes. This approach mainly aids in organizing thoughts, contemplating ideas, and making decisions, ultimately leading to analyzing information carefully to ensure that learners thoroughly grasp it and regularly evaluate the pros and cons of different ideas before making a decision. It makes the learners connect new information to personal experiences and beliefs to enhance their understanding of the concepts.

2.2 Affective

In terms of affective, the indicators were explored. The table in the next page indicates the **students' evaluation of the reflective learning style** of the respondents in terms of affective. Table 2.2 shows the results of the conducted survey

Table 2.2

Students' Evaluation of the Divergent Learning Style in terms of Affective.

Indicators	M	SD	VI
As a student, I...			
1. feel personally motivated to understand the concepts being taught in class.	3.32	.63	Strongly Agree
2. experience a sense of satisfaction when I connect new information to my own experiences and beliefs.	3.21	.69	Agree
3. find myself developing a deeper appreciation for the subject matter as I engage in reflective thinking.	3.11	.77	Agree
4. am more likely to retain information when I take the time to reflect on it and make it meaningful to me.	3.14	.73	Agree
5. feel a sense of empowerment when I use reflective thinking to enhance my understanding and personal growth.	3.16	.68	Agree
6. am more confident in my ability to apply new information to real-world situations after engaging in reflective thinking.	3.10	.65	Agree
7. find myself developing a stronger sense of self-awareness as I reflect on my learning experiences.	3.52	.39	Strongly Agree
8. am more open to consider multiple perspectives as I engage in reflective thinking.	3.20	.65	Agree
9. appreciate the opportunity to express my personal thoughts and reflections in the classroom.	3.13	.76	Agree
10. feel valued and respected when my reflective contributions are acknowledged and encouraged in the learning environment.	3.44	.61	Strongly Agree
General Weighted Mean	3.23	.10	Agree

M-(mean), VI-(verbal interpretation), SD-(standard deviation), 4.00-3.25- (strongly agree), 3.24-2.50- (agree), 2.49-1.75 - (disagree), 1.74-1.00- (strongly disagree)

Table 2.2 presents the indicators of the student's evaluation of the reflective learning style in terms of affective. Based on the result, the learners strongly agree that *they are finding themselves developing a stronger sense of self-awareness as they reflect on their learning experiences*, which obtained the highest mean of **3.52** and standard deviation of 0.39, and that *they feel valued*. Moreover, *they respected when their reflective contributions were acknowledged and encouraged in the learning environment*, with a mean of **3.44** and a standard deviation of 0.61. Moreover, they also agreed that *they are developing a deeper appreciation for the*

subject matter as they engage in reflective thinking, with a mean of **3.11** and a standard deviation of 0.77. *They are more confident in their ability to apply new information to real-world situations after engaging in reflective thinking*, with a mean of **3.10** and a standard deviation of 0.65.

Overall, based on the result of Table 2.2, it appears that most of the respondents agree that using the Reflective learning style can be beneficial in terms of affective factors such as developing a stronger sense of self-awareness, feeling valued and respected when their suggestions and ideas are acknowledged, developing a deeper appreciation for the subject matter and be more confident in their ability to apply new information to real-world situations.

According to Chan et al. (2021), Reflection helps students to understand themselves better. It was stated in the study that reflective learning provides an essential foundation for students to resolve uncertainties and complex situations better, as well as consider multiple solutions to a single problem, and it guides students to become more self-aware of their actions, strengths, and weaknesses and helping students identify their needs. In addition, Chan et al. (2021) also mentioned that using reflective learning allows the student to apply their skills in terms of problem-solving and critical thinking.

Overall, the findings of Chan et al. (2021) support the result of the study presented in Table 2.2, which suggests that students benefit from using reflective learning styles in various ways, including developing a sense of self-awareness

that enhances their understanding and personal growth, motivation and confidence in expressing their thoughts and reflections in the class. This helps the learners to have a learning environment that will encourage them to apply their reflection and knowledge in real-world situations.

2.3 Psychomotor

In terms of psychomotor, the indicators were explored. The table below indicates the **students' evaluation of the reflective learning style** in terms of psychomotor. Table 2.3 shows the results of the conducted survey.

Table 2.3
Students' Evaluation of the Reflective Learning Style in terms of Psychomotor.

Indicators	M	SD	VI
As a student, I...			
1. can apply the concepts learned in class to perform physical tasks effectively.	3.27	.64	Strongly Agree
2. try to identify the key concepts and principles I learn during hands-on activities.	3.22	.65	Agree
3. share my reflections with others to gain different perspectives on my learning.	3.17	.76	Agree
4. can effectively use what I have learned from my experiences through writing, drawing, and other mediums.	3.05	.74	Agree
5. can think back on the lessons I have learned from my experiences to come up with a better idea, solution, or answer.	3.24	.67	Agree
6. can do things smoothly and consistently through analyzing my performance and identifying areas for improvement.	3.14	.65	Agree
7. reflect on my process and explore ways to refine my skills and achieve perfect control.	3.16	.75	Agree
8. can create something unique and original by reflecting and adapting existing ideas.	3.13	.67	Agree
9. learn effectively by observing others, but I prioritize internalizing the skills and adapting them to my strengths and learning preferences.	3.40	.58	Strongly Agree
10. can review by reflecting on the concepts that have been taught to the class.	3.20	.68	Agree
General Weighted Mean	3.20	.05	Agree

M-(mean), *VI*-(verbal interpretation), *SD*-(standard deviation), 4.00-3.25- (strongly agree), 3.24-2.50- (agree), 2.49-1.75 – (disagree), 1.74-1.00- (strongly disagree)

Table 2.3 presents the indicators of the student's evaluation of the reflective learning style in terms of Psychomotor. The respondents stated, based on the result, Strongly Agree that *they learn effectively by observing others, but they prioritize internalizing the skills and adapting them to their strengths and learning preferences*, which obtained the highest mean of **3.40** with a standard deviation of 0.58, and that *they apply the concepts learned in class to perform physical tasks effectively* with the mean of **3.27** and standard deviation of 0.64, moreover, the respondents also agree that *they are creating something unique and original by reflecting and adapting existing ideas* with the mean of **3.13** and standard deviation of 0.67, also that *they effectively use what they have learned from their experiences through writing, drawing, and other mediums* with the mean of **3.05** and standard deviation of 0.74

Overall, based on the result of Table 2.3, it is seen that most of the respondents do agree that using reflective learning style helps to learn effectively by observing others, but prioritize internalizing the skills and adapting them to their strengths and learning preferences; the learners apply the concepts learned in class to perform physical tasks effectively, creating something unique and original by reflecting and adapting existing ideas, and can effectively use what the learners have learned from their experiences through writing, drawing, and other mediums.

According to McCoy (2013) found that students learned through active and reflective engagement with other learners with their ideas and surroundings.

Additionally, a study by Hwang et al. (2019) found that learning happens in social contexts, and knowledge advances from engagement in a social community.

Overall, the findings of McCoy (2013) and a study by Hwang et al. (2019) suggest that the reflective learning style underscores the significance of active participation, reflection, and social interaction in effective learning. The study findings are consistent with the results identified in Table 2.3, which suggest that reflective learning styles can be an effective strategy for enhancing learners' skills, such as applying the concepts that were learned in class such as by observing others. However, learners prioritize internalizing their skills and adapting them to their strengths and learning preferences to perform effectively, then share their reflection with others to gain different perspectives and create something unique by using the ideas from others and their existing ideas, as well as applying the concepts learned in class to perform physical tasks effectively.

3. Significant difference between divergent learning styles and reflective learning styles.

The researchers determined the significant differences between divergent learning styles and reflective learning styles of the selected Junior High School at Ulango Integrated School. The significant differences were determined using the Paired T-test. Table 3 shows the results of the conducted survey.

Table 3
Significant Differences between Divergent and Reflective Learning Styles

Variables	Mean	Std. Deviation	T	Df	Sig. (2- tailed)	Decision (H ₀)	Interpretation
Divergent and Reflective Learning Styles	0.05	0.29	2.23	14 4	0.02 7	Reject H ₀	Significant t

Table 3 presents the differences between divergent learning styles and reflective learning styles of the selected Junior High School. In terms of Divergent Learning Styles and Reflective Learning Styles, the mean difference between Divergent and Reflective Learning Styles is significant at $\alpha = 0.05$ with a 'Sig. (2-tailed)' or $p < \mathbf{0.05}$. Divergent and Reflective Learning Styles do differ statistically significantly, $t(144) = 2.23$, $p = 0.027$. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected. This means that there were significant differences between the divergent learning and reflective learning styles.

The table in the study matches aspects of divergent and reflective learning styles among junior high school students. The result shows a statistically significant difference in both strategies among students. This variation can suggest

that junior high school pupils prefer one type over another. For both divergent and reflective learners, it creates a more learning environment like inclusive environment that can benefit all junior high schools. The teachers can do different activities such as role playing, sharing, discussion and collaboration that involve both divergent and reflective learning styles. The school can do a seminar and training programs that involve divergent and reflective learning styles since it can benefit the students from junior high school.

Based on the identification of learning styles, teachers and institutions can collaborate to develop instructional approaches that facilitate the teaching and learning process. This fosters stronger connections and adaptability between the teachers and students. Ultimately promoting intellectual development of the main objectives of education. In this sense, McCarthy (2016) pointed out that learning styles have been the focus of many studies over the past 30 years to improve institutional course design and understand how students learn. The study found that both divergent and reflective learning styles can have a significant impact on students' learning styles.

Fatemeh and Camellia's (2018) study revealed that students prefer learning with divergent learning styles, as it enhances students' academic achievement. Magulod Jr. (2019) also researched learning styles and academic performance

and found a significant relationship between learning styles and the academic performance of students.

Based on the identification of learning styles, teachers and institutions can collaborate to develop instructional approaches that facilitate the teaching and learning process. This fosters stronger connections and adaptability between the teachers and students. Learners ultimately promote the intellectual development of the main objectives of education. The most comprehensive definition of the learning process suggests that the experience results in lasting changes in attitudes or patterns of behavior. Unlike talent, which is a natural aptitude, learning styles refer to preferred methods of acquiring knowledge. The study likely focused on how divergent and reflective learning styles influence student learning. Studies suggest that instruction that integrates divergent and reflective learning approaches can enhance overall comprehension and increase overall instructional efficacy. This is due to the fact that divergent learning, which involves high school students' first creative exploration of concepts, enables them to participate in more concentrated reflection during the learning process.

Overall, these studies indicate that students can develop creativity and critical thinking skills. This enables them to generate original ideas through divergent thinking and subsequently analyze these ideas through reflective thinking. Following the usage of both strategies, the students can reflect and

assess using both strategies. It is essential to consider that both strategies are adequate for the learners. The context and characteristics of the learners are essential when determining the most effective learning style.

4. Based on the study, what plan can be proposed to enhance the students' divergent and reflective learning styles?

Proposed Action Plan to enhance the divergent learning style and reflective learning style

Key Areas	Goals/Objectives	Activities	Person Involved	Time Frame	Resources Needed	Success Indicator
Divergent Learning Style	To maintain an environment where no idea is wrong in this phase.	Seminar/Webinar	School	5 to 6 months when the academic year started.	Supervision Training Internet	80% Positive feedback from the students.
	To improve their learning style and strategies in studying.	Training Programs	Teachers	6 to 7 months when the academic year start.	Educational Materials	85% Positive comments and feedback from the students.
	To encourage that all voices can be heard and all the ideas are gathered.	Team Building, sports, and joining different organizations or clubs that can help the students about their learning strategies.	Administrators Students	On-going throughout the academic year.	Sports Equipment, Educational Materials, Teachers support and Parental Support.	90% Increase student engagement in different organization or clubs. 95% of teachers and staff can identify the positive influence and have a new strategy in teaching style.
		Training to teachers and faculty staff about the positive influence of the Learning style.		Before the started of the academic year. Before the first month of the academic year.	Teachers Participation	

Key Areas	Goals/Objectives	Activities	Person Involved	Time Frame	Resources Needed	Success Indicator
	To enhance better understanding in self-reflection and personal growth.	Seminar/Webinar	School Students	5 to 6 months when the academic year started.	Facilitator and Speaker Internet	80% Positive feedback from the students.
Reflective Learning Style	To develop instructional approaches that facilitate the teaching and learning process.	Seminar/Webinar and Training Programs	School Administrators and Teachers Faculty members	6 to 7 months when the academic year start.	Facilitator and Speaker Internet Educational Materials	90% of School Administrators, Teachers, and Faculty members can identify the positive influence and have a new strategy in teaching style
	To improve their reflective learning style and strategies in studying.	Training Programs	Students	On-going throughout the academic year.	Educational Materials	85% Positive comments and feedback from the students.

Conclusions

The findings of the study highlight the distinct differences between two preferred learning styles among learners: divergent learning style and reflective learning style. The majority of participants demonstrated that these two styles are markedly different, with no significant similarities observed in their usage. Moreover, learners at Ulango Integrated School actively apply both learning styles across cognitive, affective, and psychomotor activities., underscoring their importance in educational settings.

In terms of Divergent Learning Style, the study underscores the significant benefits of incorporating divergent learning styles into educational practices. By embracing divergent activities, such as collaborative tasks and hands-on experiences, educators can empower students to cultivate multiple solutions, thereby fostering innovation, creativity, and a positive attitude toward risk-taking. Moreover, the utilization of divergent learning styles not only enhances cognitive learning but also promotes holistic personal development, as learners report improvements in memory, motivation, creativity, and performance across cognitive, affective, and psychomotor domains. Therefore, integrating divergent approaches stands as a promising strategy to enhance both learning outcomes and individual growth among students.

On the other hand, the reflective learning style proves beneficial in building knowledge, empathy, and task execution. This approach strengthens

understanding by connecting new information to personal experiences and beliefs, fostering self-awareness and a deeper appreciation for the subject matter. Moreover, learners effectively learn by observing others but prioritize personalizing skills to their strengths and preferences. With the assistance of reflective learning, students gain confidence in applying factual knowledge to real-life scenarios. Overall, this study finds that divergent and reflective learning styles benefit students' learning experiences.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions drawn from the study, several recommendations can be made to facilitate the effective implementation of divergent learning styles and reflective learning styles in educational settings.

School administrators play a crucial role in shaping education by offering activities that cater to different learning styles. This approach enhances students' critical thinking, understanding, and problem-solving abilities in cognitive, affective, and psychomotor. Administrators should provide teachers with the necessary tools and support to implement these approaches, fostering a well-rounded learning environment.

Faculty members should actively assess their student's learning needs and preferences to determine the most appropriate method for individual learners. By understanding the learners' learning styles, they should prioritize incorporating

activities that cater to divergent and reflective learning styles into their lesson plans. It should also take into account the inclusion of varied activities, like group projects and practical assignments, to inspire students' creativity and innovation.

Learners should actively engage with and embrace divergent and reflective learning styles, which are beneficial for learners in cognitive, affective, and psychomotor domains. Divergent methods foster innovation and a positive attitude towards risk-taking, while reflective approaches connect new information to personal experiences, deepening understanding and confidence in applying factual knowledge. Building strong relationships with teachers helps identify the most suitable learning style and achieve expected outcomes.

Parents must support their children's education by communicating with faculty members about their children and their progress upon integrating divergent and reflective learning styles to establish a well-rounded educational experience for learners.

Future researchers can study learners' other and complex learning styles, other respondents, other levels, and the like to understand and innovate the way of teaching and learning based on the student's preferences. They can use this study as a reference for their research.

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[The_Effect_of_Reflective-Impulsive_Conceptual_Thinking_Style_Models_and_Learning_Models_on_Learning_Outcomes_of_Complex_Analysis_by_Controlling_Students%](https://www.researchgate.net/publication/372054234_The_Effect_of_Reflective-Impulsive_Conceptual_Thinking_Style_Models_and_Learning_Models_on_Learning_Outcomes_of_Complex_Analysis_by_Controlling_Students%27_Initial_Knowledge)
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APPENDICES

Appendix A: Letter of Validation

REPUBLIC OF THE PHILIPPINES
PROVINCE OF BATANGAS
CITY GOVERNMENT OF TANAUAN

TANAUAN CITY COLLEGE

January 26, 2024

Jovet M. Moyano
MAEd-THE
Pantay Integrated High School

Sir:

We are bona fide students of Tanauan City College, taking up Bachelor of Technical-Vocational Teacher Education. We are currently conducting a study entitled “**Divergent Learning Style and Reflective Learning Style of the selected Junior High School Students**”.

In this regard, we are seeking your expertise in helping us validate the self-made questionnaire that we will use to measure the variables needed in the study. Attached here with is a copy of the questionnaire that we wish to employ in the said study. Your comments and suggestions will be highly appreciated and will be a great help to this undertaking.

We are hoping for your favorable response and wholehearted consideration regarding this matter.

Thank you so much and more power.

Very truly yours,

LIANNE A. ANDAYA

CHERRY GRACE M. CARANDANG

MARK RAVEN M. CARANDANG

ANGELICA GLODOVIZA

Researchers

Noted:

MR. ROJANE F. BERNAS
Thesis Adviser

Approved/Remarks:

JOVET M. MOYANO
MAEd-THE

REPUBLIC OF THE PHILIPPINES
 PROVINCE OF BATANGAS
CITY GOVERNMENT OF TANAUAN
TANAUAN CITY COLLEGE

January 25, 2024

Jane Bernadette M. Maligalig
 Teacher II
 Saint Benilde International School (Calamba) Inc.

Madam:

We are bona fide students of Tanauan City College, taking up Bachelor of Technical-Vocational Teacher Education. We are currently conducting a study entitled "Divergent Learning Style and Reflective Learning Style of the selected Junior High School Students".

In this regard, we are seeking your expertise in helping us validate the self-made questionnaire that we will use to measure the variables needed in the study. Attached here with is a copy of the questionnaire that we wish to employ in the said study. Your comments and suggestions will be highly appreciated and will be a great help to this undertaking.

We are hoping for your favorable response and wholehearted consideration regarding this matter.

Thank you so much and more power.

Very truly yours,

LIANNE A. ANDAYA

CHERRY GRACE M. CARANDANG

MARK RAVEN M. CARANDANG

ANGELICA GLODOVIZA

Resear chers

Noted:

MR. ROJANE F. BERNAS
 Thesis Adviser

Approved/Remarks:

JANE BERNADETTE M. MALIGALIG
 TEACHER II

January 30, 2024

Shaina Sophia R. Mendoza
Teacher III
Tanauan School of Fisheries

Madam:

We are bona fide students of Tanauan City College, taking up Bachelor of Technical-Vocational Teacher Education. We are currently conducting a study entitled "**Divergent Learning Style and Reflective Learning Style of the selected Junior High School Students**".

In this regard, we are seeking your expertise in helping us validate the ~~selfmade~~ questionnaire that we will use to measure the variables needed in the study. Attached here with is a copy of the questionnaire that we wish to employ in the said study. Your comments and suggestions will be highly appreciated and will be a great help to this undertaking

We are hoping for your favorable response and wholehearted consideration regarding this matter.

Thank you so much and more power.

Very truly yours,

LIANNE A. ANDAYA

CHERRY GRACE M. CARANDANG

MARK RAVEN M. CARANDANG

ANGELICA GLODOVIZA

Researchers

Noted:

MR. ROJANE F. BERNAS
Thesis Adviser

Approved/Remarks:

Shaina Sophia R. Mendoza
Teacher III

I.B.2	1	2	3	4
I.B.3	1	2	3	4
I.B.4	1	2	3	4
I.B.5	1	2	3	4
I.B.6	1	2	3	4
I.B.7	1	2	3	4
I.B.8	1	2	3	4
I.B.9	1	2	3	4
I.B.10	1	2	3	4

C. Psychomotor

Value Item	I.C.1	1	2	3	4
	I.C.2	1	2	3	4
	I.C.3	1	2	3	4
	I.C.4	1	2	3	4
	I.C.5	1	2	3	4
	I.C.6	1	2	3	4
	I.C.7	1	2	3	4
	I.C.8	1	2	3	4
	I.C.9	1	2	3	4
	I.C.10	1	2	3	4

II. Reflective Learning Style

A. Cognitive

Value item	II.A.1	1	2	3	4
	II.A.2	1	2	3	4
	II.A.3	1	2	3	4
	II.A.4	1	2	3	4
	II.A.5	1	2	3	4
	II.A.6	1	2	3	4

	II.A.7	1	2	3	4
	II.A.8	1	2	3	4
	II.A.9	1	2	3	4
	II.A.10	1	2	3	4
B. Affective					
Value item	II.B.1	1	2	3	4
	II.B.2	1	2	3	4
	II.B.3	1	2	3	4
	II.B.4	1	2	3	4
	II.B.5	1	2	3	4
	II.B.6	1	2	3	4
	II.B.7	1	2	3	4
	II.B.8	1	2	3	4
	II.B.9	1	2	3	4
	II.B.10	1	2	3	4
C. Psychomotor					
Value Item	II.C.1	1	2	3	4
	II.C.2	1	2	3	4
	II.C.3	1	2	3	4
	II.C.4	1	2	3	4
	II.C.5	1	2	3	4
	II.C.6	1	2	3	4
	II.C.7	1	2	3	4
	II.C.8	1	2	3	4
	II.C.9	1	2	3	4
	II.C.10	1	2	3	4

Remarks/Recommendation

Follow the comments and suggestions indicated. Once edited, you may now proceed in conducting your survey and gather the needed data. Since there is no Filipino/Tagalog translation on your questionnaire, be ready in entertaining students' queries. I hope you will finish this research! Congratulations in advance.

Overall Rating

Please check (✓) appropriate rating.

- _____ Approved to be used as presented
 _____ ✓ Approved to be used with revisions as indicated
 _____ Disapproved, the researchers must make another questionnaire

Questionnaire Validation Sheet

Name of Validator : Jane Bernadette M. Maligalig
 Highest Educational Qualification : College Graduate
 Position Held : High School Teacher
 Field of Specialization : St. Benilde International School
 Signature :

Directions:

A. Refer to the attached research instrument for validation.

B. Please use the Rating scale below and encircle the number that corresponds to the evaluation of each value item.

4	-	very valid	2	-	less valid
3	-	moderately valid	1	-	need for revalidation

I. Divergent Learning Style

A. Cognitive

Value item	IA.1	1	2	3	4
	IA.1	1	2	3	4
	IA.2	1	2	3	4
	IA.3	1	2	3	4
	IA.4	1	2	3	4
	IA.5	1	2	3	4
	IA.6	1	2	3	4
	IA.7	1	2	3	4
	IA.8	1	2	3	4
	IA.9	1	2	3	4
	IA.10	1	2	3	4

B. Affective

Value item	I.B.1	1	2	3	4
	I.B.2	1	2	3	4
	I.B.3	1	2	3	4
	I.B.4	1	2	3	4
	I.B.5	1	2	3	4
	I.B.6	1	2	3	4
	I.B.7	1	2	3	4
	I.B.8	1	2	3	4
	I.B.9	1	2	3	4
	I.B.10	1	2	3	4

C. Psychomotor

Value Item	I.C.1	1	2	3	4
	I.C.2	1	2	3	4
	I.C.3	1	2	3	4
	I.C.4	1	2	3	4
	I.C.5	1	2	3	4
	I.C.6	1	2	3	4
	I.C.7	1	2	3	4
	I.C.8	1	2	3	4
	I.C.9	1	2	3	4
	I.C.10	1	2	3	4

II. Reflective Learning Style

A. Cognitive

Value item	II.A.1	1	2	3	4
	II.A.2	1	2	3	4
	II.A.3	1	2	3	4
	II.A.4	1	2	3	4

	II.A.5	1	2	3	(4)
	II.A.6	1	2	3	(4)
	II.A.7	1	2	3	(4)
	II.A.8	1	2	3	(4)
	II.A.9	1	2	3	(4)
	II.A.10	1	2	3	(4)
B. Affective					
Value item	II.B.1	1	2	3	(4)
	II.B.2	1	2	3	(4)
	II.B.3	1	2	3	(4)
	II.B.4	1	2	3	(4)
	II.B.5	1	2	3	(4)
	II.B.6	1	2	3	(4)
	II.B.7	1	2	3	(4)
	II.B.8	1	2	3	(4)
	II.B.9	1	2	3	(4)
	II.B.10	1	2	3	(4)
C. Psychomotor					
Value Item	II.C.1	1	2	3	(4)
	II.C.2	1	2	3	(4)
	II.C.3	1	2	3	(4)
	II.C.4	1	2	3	(4)
	II.C.5	1	2	3	(4)
	II.C.6	1	2	3	(4)
	II.C.7	1	2	3	(4)
	II.C.8	1	2	3	(4)
	II.C.9	1	2	3	(4)
	II.C.10	1	2	3	(4)

Remarks/Recommendation

To prevent confusion, make sure the goods and instructions are precise and clear. Contextualizing questions or the use of examples can help respondents grasp the purpose of each item. Stress how important it is to respond with sincerity and consideration. In order to promote honest and truthful criticism, remind respondents that their answers will remain anonymous and confidential.

Overall Rating

Please check (✓) appropriate rating.

- _____✓_____ Approved to be used as presented
 _____ Approved to be used with revisions as indicated
 _____ Disapproved, the researchers must make another questionnaire

C. Psychomotor

Value Item	I.C.1	1	2	3	4
	I.C.2	1	2	3	4
	I.C.3	1	2	3	4
	I.C.4	1	2	3	4
	I.C.5	1	2	3	4
	I.C.6	1	2	3	4
	I.C.7	1	2	3	4
	I.C.8	1	2	3	4
	I.C.9	1	2	3	4
	I.C.10	1	2	3	4

II. Reflective Learning Style

A. Cognitive

Value Item	II.A.1	1	2	3	4
	II.A.2	1	2	3	4
	II.A.3	1	2	3	4
	II.A.4	1	2	3	4
	II.A.5	1	2	3	4
	II.A.6	1	2	3	4
	II.A.7	1	2	3	4
	II.A.8	1	2	3	4
	II.A.9	1	2	3	4
	II.A.10	1	2	3	4

B. Affective

Value Item	II.B.1	1	2	3	4
	II.B.2	1	2	3	4
	II.B.3	1	2	3	4
	II.B.4	1	2	3	4
	II.B.5	1	2	3	4
	II.B.6	1	2	3	4
	II.B.7	1	2	3	4
	II.B.8	1	2	3	4
	II.B.9	1	2	3	4
	II.B.10	1	2	3	4

C. Psychomotor

Value Item	II.C.1	1	2	3	4
	II.C.2	1	2	3	4
	II.C.3	1	2	3	4
	II.C.4	1	2	3	4
	II.C.5	1	2	3	4
	II.C.6	1	2	3	4

II.C.7	1	2	3	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
II.C.8	1	2	3	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
II.C.9	1	2	3	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
II.C.10	1	2	3	<input checked="" type="radio"/>

Remarks/Recommendation

The test questionnaire match test questions to Bloom's Taxonomy. This method pushes respondent to think critically and improves the thoroughness of the assessment. I recommend utilizing the test questionnaire for the research study.

Overall Rating

Please check (✓) appropriate rating.

- Approved to be used as presented
- Approved to be used with revisions as indicated
- Disapproved, the researchers must make another questionnaire

Corrections

Reflective Learning Style

Name(Optional): _____ Date: _____

Grade Level: _____

- I. **Directions:** The following are indicators that describe **Reflective Learning Style**. Using the 4 – point scale shown below, rate the following questions by placing a check in the box that corresponds to your answer. All responses that will be gathered by this research shall be treated confidential.
- 4 – Strongly Agree 3 – Agree 2 – Disagree 1 – Strongly Disagree

COGNITIVE	4	3	2	1
As a student, I...				

1. often think about how it connects to what I already know.				
2. find myself analyzing information carefully to ensure I thoroughly grasp it				
3. regularly evaluate the pros and cons of different ideas before making a decision.				
4. am inclined to reflect on my learning experiences to gain deeper insights.				
5. connect new information to my personal experiences and beliefs to enhance understanding.				
6. am drawn to considering the implications of				

6. am drawn to considering the implications of new information in real-world scenarios.				
7. find myself questioning assumptions and seeking multiple perspectives to gain a comprehensive understanding.				
8. am inclined to revisit and revise my understanding of concepts based on new information and reflections.				
9. value the process of self-reflection to enhance my learning and personal growth.				
10. am committed to continuous learning and seek opportunities to broaden my knowledge and understanding				

Aligned to Bloom's Psychomotor Taxonomy from Himberg, Brooks & Shephard (2022).

 Shaina Sophia Me...
12:59 PM Jan 30

All responses that will be gathered by this research will be treated as confidential.

 Jovet Moyano
10:30 PM Jan 25

often think about how new information is somewhat connected to what I already know.

 Shaina Sophia Me...
12:29 PM Jan 30

find myself analyzing information carefully to ensure I thoroughly grasp it.

 Jovet Moyano
10:28 PM Jan 25

remove this, replace with the word "consider"

 Jovet Moyano
10:26 PM Jan 25

this is more likely under affective domain. Use the word understand instead.

10. am committed to continuous learning and seek opportunities to broaden my knowledge and understanding				
--	--	--	--	--

Aligned to Bloom's Psychomotor Taxonomy from Himberg, Brooks & Shephard (2022).

AFFECTIVE	4	3	2	1
As a student, I...				
11. feel personally motivated to understand the concepts being taught in class.				
12. experience a sense of satisfaction when I connect new information to my own experiences and beliefs.				

PSYCHOMOTOR	4	3	2	1
As a student, I...				
21. I am able to apply the concepts learned in class to perform physical tasks effectively.				
22. try to identify the key concepts and principles I learned during hands-on activities.				

18. am more open to considering multiple perspectives as I engage in reflective thinking.				
19. appreciate the opportunity to express my personal thoughts and reflections in the classroom.				

23. share my reflections with others to gain different perspectives on my learning.				
24. can effectively use what I have learned from my experiences through writing, drawing, and other mediums				
25. can think back on the lessons I've learned from my experiences to come up with a better idea, solution, or answer.				
26. analyze my performance, identify areas for improvement and potential errors until I can do things smoothly and consistently.				
27. reflect on my process and exploring ways to refine my skills and achieved perfect control.				
28. reflect on existing ideas and adapt to create something unique and original.				
29. learn effectively by observing others, but I prioritize internalizing the skills and adapting them to my own strengths and learning preferences.				

10:26 PM Jan 25
this is more likely under affective domain. Use the word understand instead.

 Shaina Sophia Me...
12:32 PM Jan 30
am committed to continuous learning and seeking opportunities to broaden my knowledge and understanding.

 Jovet Moyano
10:39 PM Jan 25
remove this since I is already mentioned/stated in the beginning statement.

 Shaina Sophia Me...
12:35 PM Jan 30
can apply the concepts learned in class to perform physical tasks effectively.

 Jovet Moyano
10:47 PM Jan 25
consider

 Shaina Sophia Me...
12:36 PM Jan 30
try to identify the key concepts and principles I learn during hands-on activities.

 Jovet Moyano
10:40 PM Jan 25
this is more likely under cognitive domain. Use the word "apply" instead.

 Shaina Sophia Me...
12:36 PM Jan 30
can effectively use what I have learned from my experiences through writing, drawing, and other mediums.

26. analyze my performance, identify areas for improvement and potential errors until I can do things smoothly and consistently.				
27. reflect on my process and exploring ways to refine my skills and achieved perfect control.				
28. reflect on existing ideas and adapt to create something unique and original.			1	
29. learn effectively by observing others, but I prioritize internalizing the skills and adapting them to my own strengths and learning preferences.				
30. can review by reflecting about the concept that has been taught to the class.				

Aligned to Bloom's Psychomotor Taxonomy from Himberg, Brooks & Shephard (2022)

27. reflect on my process and exploring ways to refine my skills and achieved perfect control.				
28. reflect on existing ideas and adapt to create something unique and original.				
29. learn effectively by observing others, but I prioritize internalizing the skills and adapting them to my own strengths and learning preferences.				
30. can review by reflecting about the concept that has been taught to the class.				

Aligned to Bloom's Psychomotor Taxonomy from Himberg, Brooks & Shephard (2022)

27. reflect on my process and exploring ways to refine my skills and achieved perfect control.				
28. reflect on existing ideas and adapt to create something unique and original.				
29. learn effectively by observing others, but I prioritize internalizing the skills and adapting them to my own strengths and learning preferences.				
30. can review by reflecting about the concept				

27. reflect on my process and exploring ways to refine my skills and achieved perfect control.				
28. reflect on existing ideas and adapt to create something unique and original.				
29. learn effectively by observing others, but I prioritize internalizing the skills and adapting them to my own strengths and learning preferences.				
30. can review by reflecting about the concept that has been taught to the class.				

other mediums.

J Jovet Moyano
10:41 PM Jan 25

can do things smoothly and consistently through analyzing my performance and identifying areas for improvement.

Shaina Sophia Mendoza
12:39 PM Jan 30

analyze my performance, identify areas for improvement, and identify potential errors until I can do things smoothly and consistently.

Shaina Sophia Me... ✓
12:39 PM Jan 30

reflect on my process and explore ways to refine my skills and achieve perfect control.

Reply or add others with @

👍 🤔

10:41 PM Jan 25

J Jovet Moyano ✓
10:41 PM Jan 25

explore

Reply or add others with @

Ok Thanks 🤔

10:41 PM Jan 25

J Jovet Moyano ✓
10:41 PM Jan 25

achieve

Reply or add others with @

Ok Done 👍

12:39 PM Jan 30

28. reflect on existing ideas and adapt to create something unique and original.				
29. learn effectively by observing others, but I prioritize internalizing the skills and adapting them to my own strengths and learning preferences.				
30. can review by reflecting about the concept that has been taught to the class.				

Aligned to Bloom's Psychomotor Taxonomy from Himberg, Brooks & Shephard (2022).

28. reflect on existing ideas and adapt to create something unique and original.				
29. learn effectively by observing others, but I prioritize internalizing the skills and adapting them to my own strengths and learning preferences.				
30. can review by reflecting about the concept that has been taught to the class.				

Aligned to Bloom's Psychomotor Taxonomy from Himberg, Brooks & Shephard (2022).

30. can review by reflecting about the concept that has been taught to the class.				
---	--	--	--	--

Aligned to Bloom's Psychomotor Taxonomy from Himberg, Brooks & Shephard (2022).

Shaina Sophia Me... 12:39 PM Jan 30

reflect on existing ideas and adapt them to create something unique and original.

Reply or add others with @

Or something like that

Jovet Moyano 10:42 PM Jan 25

can create something unique and original by reflecting and adapting existing ideas.

Reply or add others with @

Or something like that

12:40 PM Jan 30

Shaina Sophia Me... 12:40 PM Jan 30

can review by reflecting on the concepts that have been taught to the class.

Reply or add others with @

Ok Done

Divergent Learning Style

3. am open to considering new ideas and perspectives, even if they challenge my existing beliefs.				
4. find myself seeking out diverse viewpoints to enrich my understanding and problem-solving abilities.				
5. am drawn to exploring multiple solutions to problems, considering both conventional and				
5. am drawn to exploring multiple solutions to problems, considering both conventional and unconventional approaches.				
6. am comfortable with ambiguity and uncertainty, embracing the open-ended nature of creative thinking.				
7. find it exciting to generate innovative ideas and explore uncharted territories in my thinking.				

Jovet Moyano 10:49 PM Jan 25

in considering

Reply or add others with @

Ok Done Thanks

Jovet Moyano 10:50 PM Jan 25

remove this and use the word "suggest" instead.

Reply or add others with @

Ok Agreed Done

9. value the power of divergent thinking in generating novel solutions and fostering creativity.				
10. am committed to cultivating my divergent thinking skills to enhance my problem-solving and innovative potential.				

Aligned to Bloom's Psychomotor Taxonomy from Himberg, Brooks & Shephard (2022).

	4	3	2	1
10. am committed to cultivating my divergent thinking skills to enhance my problem-solving and innovative potential.				

Aligned to Bloom's Psychomotor Taxonomy from Himberg, Brooks & Shephard (2022).

AFFECTIVE	4	3	2	1
As a student, I...				
11. feel energized and excited when I am encouraged to generate multiple ideas and				
16. feel a sense of belonging and community when I participate in divergent thinking activities in the classroom.				
17. am more likely to engage with the learning material when I am encouraged to explore different perspectives and approaches.				

20. am committed to developing my divergent thinking skills to enhance my problem-solving and creative potential.				
---	--	--	--	--

Aligned to Bloom's Psychomotor Taxonomy from Himberg, Brooks & Shephard (2022).

PSYCHOMOTOR	4	3	2	1
As a student, I...				
21. am able to generate multiple strategies and approaches to solving physical tasks.				
22. try new things and experiment with different materials and techniques during hands-on activities.				
23. am drawn to hands-on activities that challenge me to think outside the box.				
24. can effectively express my ideas creatively through writing, drawing, or other mediums.				

J Jovet Moyano 10:54 PM Jan 25 ✓ ⋮

this is more likely under affective domain. Use the word "extend" instead.

Reply or add others with @

Ok Thanks 🙌

J Jovet Moyano 10:52 PM Jan 25 ✓ ⋮

change this. Use "to develop"

Reply or add others with @

Ok Done Thanks

J Jovet Moyano 10:54 PM Jan 25 ✓ ⋮

remove this

change belonging to belongingness

Reply or add others with @

Ok Done Agreed

J Jovet Moyano 10:55 PM Jan 25 ✓ ⋮

to develop

Reply or add others with @

Done Ok Thanks

J Jovet Moyano 10:56 PM Jan 25 ✓ ⋮

in solving

Reply or add others with @

Done Ok Thanks

23. am drawn to hands-on activities that challenge me to think outside the box.				
24. can effectively express my ideas creatively through writing, drawing, or other mediums.				
25. can collaborate with others using physical means to generate and develop creative ideas.				
26. like to practice until I can do things smoothly and consistently.				
27. enjoy refining my skills and achieving perfect control.				
28. can create something entirely new and				

29. learn by watching and repeating exactly				
30. Can review by using different way such as creating flashcard, peer study and creating scenario.				

Aligned to Bloom's Psychomotor Taxonomy from Himberg, Brooks & Shephard (2022).

30. Can review by using different way such as creating flashcard, peer study and creating scenario.				
---	--	--	--	--

Aligned to Bloom's Psychomotor Taxonomy from Himberg, Brooks & Shephard (2022).

Appendix B: Research Instrument

Dear Respondents,

We are bona fide students of Tanauan City College, taking up Bachelor of Technical-Vocational Teacher Education. We are currently conducting a study entitled “Divergent Learning Style and Reflective Learning Style of the Selected Junior High School Students”.

Be assured that the information you provide will be used for this study alone and will be treated confidentially. With your cooperation, we are grateful. Thank you, and May God bless you.

The Researchers

- I. **Directions:** The following are indicators that describe **Divergent Learning Style**. Using the 4 – point scale shown below, rate the following questions by placing a check in the box that corresponds to your answer. All responses that will be gathered by this research will be treated as confidential.

4 – Strongly Agree 3 – Agree 2 – Disagree 1 – Strongly Disagree

DIVERGENT LEARNING STYLE

COGNITIVE	4	3	2	1
As a student, I...				

1. am naturally inclined to generate multiple ideas, even if they seem unconventional or impractical.				
2. am consciously evaluate multiple alternatives and select the most appropriate one after careful consideration.				
3. am open in considering new ideas and perspectives, even if they challenge my existing beliefs.				
4. find myself seeking out diverse viewpoints to enrich my understanding and problem-solving abilities.				
5. suggest multiple solutions to problems, considering both conventional and unconventional approaches.				
6. am comfortable with ambiguity and uncertainty, embracing the open-ended nature of creative thinking.				
7. find it exciting to generate innovative ideas and explore uncharted territories in my thinking.				
8. usually question the ways of thinking to come up with new and creative ideas.				
9. extend the power of divergent thinking in generating novel solutions and fostering creativity.				
10. am committed to develop my divergent thinking skills to enhance my problem-solving and innovative potential.				

Aligned to Bloom's Psychomotor Taxonomy from Himberg, Brooks & Shephard (2022).

AFFECTIVE	4	3	2	1
As a student, I...				
11. feel energized and excited when I am encouraged to generate multiple ideas and explore different possibilities.				
12. find immense satisfaction in participating in brainstorming sessions where I feel free to express my unique ideas, not having any burden by the fear of criticism or judgment.				
13. feel a sense of accomplishment when I come up with innovative solutions or unconventional approaches to problems.				
14. find myself developing a more positive attitude towards risk-taking and embracing uncertainty in the learning process.				
15. appreciate the opportunity to collaborate with others as I can conceptualize the connection from different perspectives.				
16. feel a sense of belongingness when I participate in divergent thinking activities in the classroom.				
17. am more likely to engage with the learning material when I am encouraged to explore different perspectives and approaches.				
18. find myself developing a stronger sense of creativity and innovation as I engage in divergent thinking activities.				
19. appreciate the value of divergent thinking in fostering open-mindedness and adaptability to change.				
20. am committed to develop my divergent thinking skills to enhance my problem-solving and creative potential.				

Aligned to Bloom's Psychomotor Taxonomy from Himberg, Brooks & Shephard (2022).

PSYCHOMOTOR	4	3	2	1
As a student, I...				
21. am able to generate multiple strategies and approaches in solving physical tasks.				
22. try new things and experiment with different materials and techniques during hands-on activities.				
23. participate during hands-on activities and this challenge me to think outside the box.				
24. can effectively express my ideas creatively through writing, drawing, or other mediums.				
25. can collaborate with others using physical means to generate and develop creative ideas.				
26. like to practice until I can do things smoothly and consistently.				
27. enjoy refining my skills and achieving perfect control.				
28. can create something entirely new and original.				
29. learn by watching and imitating exactly what is being demonstrated.				
30. can review in different ways, such as by creating flashcards, doing peer study, and creating scenarios.				

Aligned to Bloom's Psychomotor Taxonomy from Himberg, Brooks & Shephard (2022).

- II. **Directions:** The following are indicators that describe **Reflective Learning Style**. Using the 4 – point scale shown below, rate the following questions by placing a check in the box that corresponds to your answer. All responses that will be gathered by this research will be treated as confidential.

4 – Strongly Agree 3 – Agree 2 – Disagree 1 – Strongly Disagree

REFLECTIVE LEARNING STYLE

COGNITIVE	4	3	2	1
As a student, I...				
1. often think about how new information is somewhat connected to what I already know.				
2. find myself analyzing information carefully to ensure I thoroughly grasp it.				
3. regularly evaluate the pros and cons of different ideas before making a decision.				
4. am inclined to reflect on my learning experiences to gain deeper insights.				
5. connect new information to my personal experiences and beliefs to enhance understanding.				
6. am drawn to consider the implications of new information in real-world scenarios.				
7. find myself questioning assumptions and seeking multiple perspectives to gain a comprehensive understanding.				
8. am inclined to revisit and revise my understanding of concepts based on new information and reflections.				

9. understand the process of self-reflection to enhance my learning and personal growth.				
10. am committed to continuous learning and seeking opportunities to broaden my knowledge and understanding.				

Aligned to Bloom's Psychomotor Taxonomy from Himberg, Brooks & Shephard (2022).

AFFECTIVE	4	3	2	1
As a student, I ...				
11. feel personally motivated to understand the concepts being taught in class.				
12. experience a sense of satisfaction when I connect new information to my own experiences and beliefs.				
13. find myself developing a deeper appreciation for the subject matter as I engage in reflective thinking.				
14. am more likely to retain information when I take the time to reflect on it and make it meaningful to me.				
15. feel a sense of empowerment when I use reflective thinking to enhance my understanding and personal growth.				
16. am more confident in my ability to apply new information to real-world situations after engaging in reflective thinking.				
17. find myself developing a stronger sense of self-awareness as I reflect on my learning experiences.				
18. am more open to consider multiple perspectives as I engage in reflective thinking.				

19. appreciate the opportunity to express my personal thoughts and reflections in the classroom.				
20. feel valued and respected when my reflective contributions are acknowledged and encouraged in the learning environment.				

Aligned to Bloom's Psychomotor Taxonomy from Himberg, Brooks & Shephard (2022).

PSYCHOMOTOR	4	3	2	1
As a student, I...				
21. can apply the concepts learned in class to perform physical tasks effectively.				
22. try to identify the key concepts and principles I learn during hands-on activities.				
23. share my reflections with others to gain different perspectives on my learning.				
24. can effectively use what I have learned from my experiences through writing, drawing, and other mediums.				
25. can think back on the lessons I've learned from my experiences to come up with a better idea, solution, or answer.				
26. can do things smoothly and consistently through analyzing my performance and identifying areas for improvement.				
27. reflect on my process and explore ways to refine my skills and achieve perfect control.				
28. can create something unique and original by reflecting and adapting existing ideas.				

29. learn effectively by observing others, but I prioritize internalizing the skills and adapting them to my own strengths and learning preferences.				
30. can review by reflecting on the concepts that have been taught to the class.				

Aligned to Bloom's Psychomotor Taxonomy from Himberg, Brooks & Shephard (2022).

**Appendix C: Result of Pearson's R
VALIDITY TEST
VALIDITY TEST RESULT**

RESEARCH TITLE:	DIVERGENT LEARNING STYLE AND REFLECTIVE LEARNING STYLE OF THE SELECTED JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS
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To test the validity of the questionnaire, the statistician utilized **Pearson's *r* Correlation**. According to Ahrens et al. (2020), to assess construct validity, Pearson's correlation can be employed. Pearson's correlation is commonly used to verify the intensity of the existing linear association between variables, and it measures the linear association between quantitative variables.

The table below shows the critical values for Pearson's *r*. This table will be use as reference to interpret the significance of each variables/indicator to come up with an interpretation.

Table for Critical values of Pearson's r

<i>For a two-tailed test</i>				
df:	0.1	0.05	0.02	0.01
1	.988	.997	.9995	.9999
2	.9	.95	.98	.99
3	.805	.878	.934	.959
4	.729	.811	.882	.917
5	.669	.754	.833	.874
6	.622	.707	.789	.834
7	.582	.666	.75	.798
8	.549	.632	.716	.765
9	.521	.602	.685	.735
10	.497	.576	.658	.708
11	.476	.553	.634	.684
12	.458	.532	.612	.661
13	.441	.514	.592	.641
14	.426	.497	.574	.623
15	.412	.482	.558	.606
16	.4	.468	.542	.59
17	.389	.456	.528	.575
18	.378	.444	.516	.561
19	.369	.433	.503	.549
20	.36	.423	.492	.537
21	.352	.413	.482	.526
22	.344	.404	.472	.515
23	.337	.396	.462	.505
24	.33	.388	.453	.496
25	.323	.381	.445	.487
26	.317	.374	.437	.479
27	.311	.367	.43	.471
28	.306	.361	.423	.463
29	.301	.355	.416	.456
30	.296	.349	.409	.449

Using this table as reference, calculating the degrees of freedom where $30 - N = 28$, we compare the computed p value to the critical values in the Pearson's r table. To interpret the test as valid, $p > df$, where the df is 28, with a 95% confidence (0.05).

The following are the results of the validity test using Pearson's r Coefficient to test the construct validity of each indicator in the research question.

For the second test, the statistician utilized the Pearson's r Coefficient to test the convergent and discriminant validity of the indicators.

CONSTRUCT VALIDITY TEST

RESEARCH INSTRUMENT

Correlations

		RA P1	RA P2	RA P3	RA P4	RA P5	RA P6	RA P7	RA P8	RA P9	RAP 10	RP P1	RP P2	RP P3	RP P4	RP P5	RP P6	RP P7	RP P8	RP P9	RPP 10	POSTTE ST
DCP1	Pearson Correlati on Sig. (2-tailed)	.176	.180	.162	.059	.314	-.383	-.230	-.352	-.	-.382	.282	.241	-.119	-.172	-.198	.071	-.307	-.398	-.133	.040	.372
		.353	.342	.391	.756	.091	.037	.221	.057	.755	.037	.131	.200	.531	.363	.293	.707	.099	.029	.483	.835	.043
	N	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
DCP2	Pearson Correlati on Sig. (2-tailed)	-.028	.151	.481	.050	.084	.120	.467	-.110	.296	.298	.124	.141	.147	-.225	.259	.308	.258	.435	.410	.272	.356
		.885	.426	.007	.794	.658	.529	.009	.564	-.112	-.109	.513	.456	.440	.232	-.167	.098	-.169	.016	.025	-.146	.054
	N	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
DCP3	Pearson Correlati on Sig. (2-tailed)	.086	.512	-.304	.428	.506	.161	.248	-.129	.315	.039	-.194	.078	.344	.136	.457	.103	.101	.366	.542	.617	.509
		.651	.004	.102	.018	.004	.367	.187	.497	.091	.838	.303	.881	.062	.472	.011	.587	.596	.047	.000	.000	.004
	N	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
DCP4	Pearson Correlati on Sig. (2-tailed)	.167	.457	.000	.482	.341	.559	.274	.428	.256	.301	.090	.242	.293	.501	.404	.512	.156	.425	.397	.648	.738
		.379	.011	1.000	.007	.065	.001	.143	.018	.172	.106	.635	.197	.116	.005	.027	.004	.410	.019	.030	.000	.000
	N	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
DCP5	Pearson Correlati on Sig. (2-tailed)	.188	.281	.310	.247	.436	.095	.393	.088	.052	.432	.231	.171	.273	.338	.517	.508	.032	.471	.661	.436	.565
		.320	.132	.095	.188	.016	.616	.032	.645	.783	.017	.219	.368	.144	.068	.003	.004	.867	.009	.000	.016	.001
	N	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
DCP6	Pearson Correlati on Sig. (2-tailed)	.172	.343	.189	.310	.207	.611	.359	.561	.192	.395	.211	.326	.250	.161	.378	.195	.380	.365	.140	.399	.589
		.364	.064	.317	.095	.271	.000	.051	.001	.310	.031	.262	.079	.184	.397	.039	.302	.038	.048	.462	.029	.001
	N	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
DCP7	Pearson Correlati on Sig. (2-tailed)	.153	.181	.300	.097	-.004	.438	.312	.508	.006	.545	.168	.139	.231	-.003	.075	.495	.387	.254	.061	.249	.478
		.421	.338	.108	.610	.982	.015	.093	.004	.973	.002	.376	.465	.220	.986	.694	.005	.035	.175	.747	.185	.008
	N	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
DCP8	Pearson Correlati on	.113	.195	.144	-.070	.224	-.348	-.005	-.168	-.141	-.484	.241	-.221	-.024	.038	.216	.370	-.028	.038	0.000	.140	.299

with other indicators that give further confusion to the respondents.

CONSTRUCT VALIDITY TEST – SPSS RESULT

The screenshot shows the SPSS 'Correlations' window. The main area contains a large table of Pearson correlation coefficients. The variables listed are BCP1 through BCP15. Each variable has a 'Pearson Correlation' value and an 'N' value. The table is a lower triangular matrix, with the diagonal elements all being 1.000. The values represent the correlations between each variable and every other variable in the set.

	BCP1	BCP2	BCP3	BCP4	BCP5	BCP6	BCP7	BCP8	BCP9	BCP10	BCP11	BCP12	BCP13	BCP14	BCP15
BCP1	1														
BCP2	.669	1													
BCP3	.782	.711	1												
BCP4	.729	.294	.1	1											
BCP5	.227	.712	.607	.1	1										
BCP6	.705	.284	.430	.312	.1	1									
BCP7	.614	.281	.607	.269	.681	.1	1								
BCP8	.688	.281	.619	.269	.682	.681	.1	1							
BCP9	.288	.284	.780	.808	.170	.009	.617	.1	1						
BCP10	.283	.184	.624	.268	.114	.239	.484	.1	.114	1					
BCP11	.183	.282	.111	.186	.844	.007	.869	.044	.022	.286	1				
BCP12	.287	.681	.441	.287	.380	.249	.283	.121	.827	.069	.472	1			
BCP13	.187	.341	.615	.383	.089	.180	.170	.611	.086	.088	.813	.145	1		
BCP14	.448	.331	.608	.488	.281	.088	.243	.289	.041	.888	.1	.237	.812	1	
BCP15	.288	.284	.103	.188	.084	.208	.271	.473	.084	.388	.222	.1	.307	.282	1

	Sig (2-tailed)	.26	.39	.00	.01	.01	.46	.30	.21	.30	.031	.27	.12	.15	.06	.06	.06	.00	.37	.770	.43	.00	.00	.00	.00	.78	.00	.16	.07	.004			
	N	4	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30			
	Pearson																																
	n	.01	.53	.25	.10	.05	.58	.41	.36	.27	.295	.18	.12	.35	.04	.01	.01	.10	.41	.18	.05	.1	.26	.25	.18	.21	.33	.52	.03	.17	.16		
Rap 16	Correlation	.7	.4*																														
	Sig (2-tailed)	.00	.00	.17	.58	.75	.00	.00	.05	.13	.113	.32	.51	.05	.83	.94	.57	.02	.33	.77	.5	.16	.17	.34	.24	.07	.00	.87	.34	.31	.965		
	N	1	2	0	8	9	1	2	1	9	4	5	6	1	5	1	2	7	5	3	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30		
	Pearson																																
	n	.08	.22	.30	.00	.00	0	.15	.35	.16	.24	.04	.26	.29	.06	.14	.09	.23	.08	.14	.261	1	.30	.00	.03	.38	.23	.18	.10	.04	.286		
rpp 1	Correlation																																
	Sig (2-tailed)	.86	.22	.10	1.0	1.0	.41	.08	.36	.19	.547	.80	.15	.11	1.0	.43	.83	.20	.86	.43	.163	.10	1.0	.84	.03	.21	.34	.59	.80	.190			
	N	5	5	0	30	30	8	8	1	5	0	8	8	08	4	7	6	5	5	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30		
	Pearson																																
	n	.48	.49	.12	.47	.21	.42	.28	.12	.31	.305	.13	.07	.21	.43	.41	.21	.02	.36	.48	.257	.30	.6	1	.26	.24	.27	.26	.24	.46	.24		
rpp 2	Correlation																																
	Sig (2-tailed)	.01	.00	.02	.00	.25	.02	.13	.46	.09	.080	.46	.71	.25	.01	.02	.25	.00	.04	.00	.170	.10	.00	.0	.7	.3	.9	.7	1	.0	.260		
	N	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30		
	Pearson																																
	n	.14	.33	.59	.48	.60	.27	.23	.34	.28	.260	.56	.30	.25	.64	.37	.15	.58	.29	.54	.180	.00	.36	1	.22	.34	.02	.37	.24	.25	.291		
rpp 3	Correlation																																
	Sig (2-tailed)	.44	.00	.00	.00	.14	.21	.06	.12	.051	.00	.03	.16	.00	.04	.40	.00	.11	.00	.341	1.0	.05	.00	.2	.08	.88	.04	.19	.17	.119			
	N	1	6	1	7	0	4	4	3	2	1	3	6	6	2	1	7	2	2	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30		
	Pearson																																
	n	.34	.56	.15	.15	.37	.33	.42	.16	.25	.198	.37	.35	.37	.25	.22	.00	.41	.12	.219	.03	.24	.22	1	.47	.25	.1	.23	.29	.256			
rpp 4	Correlation																																
	Sig (2-tailed)	.06	.00	.47	.41	.04	.07	.02	.37	.17	.294	.14	.05	.78	.04	.17	.24	.08	.02	.50	.245	.44	.18	.23	.00	.17	.48	.21	.11	.172			
	N	0	1	5	3	1	3	0	1	2	1	4	4	8	3	2	2	1	1	9	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30		
	Pearson																																
	n	.33	.63	.46	.67	.52	.27	.51	.27	.10	.051	.30	.51	.19	.42	.38	.36	.42	.14	.31	.321	.38	.27	.34	.47	1	.30	.10	.21	.53			
rpp 5	Correlation																																
	Sig (2-tailed)	.07	.00	.00	.88	.00	.14	.00	.13	.58	.388	.10	.00	.01	.03	.05	.01	.43	.09	.074	.03	.14	.06	.00	.00	.27	.59	.25	.00	.004			
	N	3	0	9	8	3	2	4	7	7	0	4	0	6	0	0	9	7	1	1	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30		
	Pearson																																
	n	.17	.5	.32	.47	.5	2	4	2	.37	.36	.55	.40	.338	.12	.40	.41	.06	.2	.01	.19	.39	.26	.05	.525	.23	.26	.02	.25	.20	1	.06	.47
rpp 6	Correlation																																
	Sig (2-tailed)	.35	.08	.88	.01	.58	.14	.03	.00	.00	.088	.52	.60	.02	.74	.92	.31	.03	.16	.78	.003	.21	.15	.88	.17	.27	.73	.00	.17	.073			
	N	4	1	4	9	7	6	2	1	0	0	2	2	2	6	7	2	2	0	2	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	
	Pearson																																
	n	.17	.04	.51	.38	.20	.10	.19	.14	.33	.264	.26	.09	.30	.30	.23	.46	.27	.42	.56	.030	.18	.24	.37	.13	.10	.06	1	.28	.19	.361		
rpp 7	Correlation																																
	Sig (2-tailed)	.36	.83	.30	.03	.28	.57	.31	.40	.06	.159	.15	.83	.10	.10	.20	.20	.14	.01	.00	.874	.34	.19	.04	.48	.59	.73	.12	.20	.065			
	N	6	4	4	9	5	6	0	9	0	9	4	1	4	4	9	3	9	1	1	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	
	Pearson																																
	n	.28	.44	.04	.41	.01	.40	.46	.40	.30	.173	.02	.12	.24	.28	.30	.42	.44	.41	.24	.178	.10	.40	.24	.23	.21	.47	.23	1	.48	.456		
rpp 8	Correlation																																
	Sig (2-tailed)	.12	.01	.80	.02	.93	.02	.01	.10	.380	.80	.51	.19	.03	.10	.01	.01	.02	.19	.348	.59	.01	.19	.21	.25	.00	.12	.00	.011				
	N	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30		
	Pearson																																
	n	.19	.37	.24	.00	.32	.36	.26	.27	.17	.042	.26	.36	.30	.38	.48	.19	.34	.00	.32	.192	.04	.24	.25	.29	.53	.25	.19	.46	.1	.590		
rpp 9	Correlation																																
	Sig (2-tailed)	.33	.04	.20	1.0	.08	.03	.16	.14	.34	.808	.15	.03	.08	.03	.00	.39	.05	1.0	.07	.310	.80	.20	.17	.11	.00	.17	.29	.00	.001			
	N	7	0	0	0	4	1	3	4	5	0	4	4	7	8	6	9	00	9	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30		
	Pearson																																
	n	.54	.34	.41	.39	.48	.19	.27	.40	.42	.170	.13	.30	.26	.48	.44	.58	.27	.26	.50	.013	.34	.22	.29	.25	.50	.33	.34	.45	.59			
rpp 10	Correlation																																
	Sig (2-tailed)	.00	.00	.02	.03	.00	.28	.14	.08	.02	.270	.47	.00	.18	.																		

CONVERGENT AND DISCRIMINANT VALIDITY TEST – SPSS RESULT

The image displays two screenshots of the SPSS 'Correlations' output window. Both windows show the same data for the same set of variables: DCPI1, DCPI2, DCPI3, DCPI4, DCPI5, DCPI6, DCPI7, DCPI8, DCPI9, DCPI10, DCPI11, DCPI12, DCPI13, DCPI14, DCPI15, DCPI16, DCPI17, DCPI18, DCPI19, DCPI20, DCPI21, DCPI22, DCPI23, DCPI24, DCPI25, DCPI26, DCPI27, DCPI28, DCPI29, DCPI30, DCPI31, DCPI32, DCPI33, DCPI34, DCPI35, DCPI36, DCPI37, DCPI38, DCPI39, DCPI40, DCPI41, DCPI42, DCPI43, DCPI44, DCPI45, DCPI46, DCPI47, DCPI48, DCPI49, DCPI50, DCPI51, DCPI52, DCPI53, DCPI54, DCPI55, DCPI56, DCPI57, DCPI58, DCPI59, DCPI60, DCPI61, DCPI62, DCPI63, DCPI64, DCPI65, DCPI66, DCPI67, DCPI68, DCPI69, DCPI70, DCPI71, DCPI72, DCPI73, DCPI74, DCPI75, DCPI76, DCPI77, DCPI78, DCPI79, DCPI80, DCPI81, DCPI82, DCPI83, DCPI84, DCPI85, DCPI86, DCPI87, DCPI88, DCPI89, DCPI90, DCPI91, DCPI92, DCPI93, DCPI94, DCPI95, DCPI96, DCPI97, DCPI98, DCPI99, DCPI100.

The first screenshot shows the top portion of the output, with the first 10 rows of the correlation matrix. The second screenshot shows the bottom portion of the output, with the last 10 rows of the correlation matrix. The diagonal elements are all 1.000, and the matrix is symmetric.

RELIABILITY TEST RESULT

RESEARCH TITLE:	DIVERGENT LEARNING STYLE AND REFLECTIVE LEARNING STYLE OF THE SELECTED JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS
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To test the reliability of the questionnaire, the statistician tested the *INTERNAL CONSISTENCY* of the instrument using **Cronbach's Alpha** and the instrument's *TEST-RETEST CORRELATION* using **Pearson Product-Moment Correlation**. According to Collins (2007), Cronbach's Alpha is a way of assessing reliability by comparing the amount of shared variance, or covariance, among the items making up an instrument to the amount of overall variance. The table below shows the interpretation of Cronbach's Alpha.

INTERPRETATION	
Cronbach's Alpha	Internal Consistency
$\alpha \geq 0.9$	Excellent
$0.9 > \alpha \geq 0.8$	
$0.8 > \alpha \geq 0.7$	
$0.7 > \alpha \geq 0.6$	Good
$0.6 > \alpha \geq 0.5$	Acceptable
	Questionable
	Poor
$0.5 > \alpha$	Unacceptable

The following are the results of the reliability test.

INTERNAL CONSISTENCY TEST

Cronbach's Alpha

RELIABILITY STATISTICS	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.968	90

Item-Total Statistics

	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
DC1	297.5000	890.328	-.031	.969
DC2	297.4333	881.357	.188	.968
DC3	297.1667	876.902	.269	.968
DC4	297.2000	863.683	.665	.967
DC5	297.3333	867.609	.565	.968
DC6	297.2667	874.478	.364	.968
DC7	297.2000	878.234	.348	.968
DC8	297.3000	867.114	.488	.968
DC9	297.2333	872.944	.531	.968
DC10	297.1667	860.213	.647	.967
DA1	296.9333	870.961	.493	.968
DA2	297.3000	864.769	.541	.968
DA3	297.2000	874.717	.375	.968
DA4	297.1333	872.671	.455	.968
DA5	297.0333	887.206	.053	.968
DA6	297.3333	863.402	.625	.967

DA7	297.2333	860.530	.657	.967
DA8	297.2667	864.616	.667	.967
DA9	297.1333	862.533	.738	.967
DA10	297.0333	864.171	.543	.968
DP1	297.2000	868.028	.674	.967
DP2	297.0000	866.414	.677	.967
DP3	297.3667	864.309	.576	.967
DP4	297.3333	878.506	.237	.968
DP5	297.3667	867.551	.537	.968
DP6	297.1000	868.576	.449	.968
DP7	297.1667	869.385	.507	.968
DP8	297.1667	860.351	.688	.967
DP9	297.2667	854.202	.726	.967
DP10	297.2000	865.959	.465	.968
DCP1	297.2667	877.375	.292	.968
DCP2	297.4000	876.110	.332	.968
DCP3	297.1000	873.197	.482	.968
DCP4	297.1667	861.937	.766	.967
DCP5	297.3333	870.437	.538	.968
DCP6	297.3333	869.126	.524	.968
DCP7	297.1333	876.395	.446	.968
DCP8	297.3667	876.309	.317	.968
DCP9	297.3333	875.126	.402	.968
DCP10	297.2000	858.234	.701	.967
DAP1	296.9667	871.137	.447	.968
DAP2	297.1667	879.178	.279	.968
DAP3	297.0667	871.995	.514	.968

DAP4	297.2000	874.924	.369	.968
DAP5	297.0333	883.482	.193	.968
DAP6	297.0000	862.759	.657	.967
DAP7	297.2000	861.821	.783	.967
DAP8	297.2333	862.392	.657	.967
DAP9	296.9000	871.197	.543	.968
DAP10	297.0000	874.828	.354	.968
DPP1	297.2000	865.683	.612	.967
DPP2	297.1000	864.990	.662	.967
DPP3	297.2000	868.924	.527	.968
DPP4	297.0000	870.621	.499	.968
DPP5	297.1000	874.231	.451	.968
DPP6	296.9667	871.482	.477	.968
DPP7	296.9000	878.714	.359	.968
DPP8	297.1333	863.016	.617	.967
DPP9	296.9667	864.930	.561	.968
DPP10	296.9667	876.861	.331	.968
RCP1	297.3000	869.390	.504	.968
RCP2	296.8333	870.489	.666	.967
RCP3	297.0667	871.651	.474	.968
RCP4	297.2333	867.289	.580	.967
RCP5	296.9000	869.748	.587	.967
RCP6	297.2000	872.993	.515	.968
RCP7	297.2333	869.495	.481	.968
RCP8	297.1667	864.695	.629	.967
RCP9	297.1000	867.748	.538	.968
RCP10	297.1333	872.051	.401	.968

RAP1	297.0667	877.789	.340	.968
RAP2	297.1000	867.128	.603	.967
RAP3	296.9000	877.679	.347	.968
RAP4	297.0333	864.654	.663	.967
RAP5	297.1333	873.775	.471	.968
RAP6	297.3000	870.079	.531	.968
RAP7	297.2333	864.944	.594	.967
RAP8	297.3000	871.045	.461	.968
RAP9	297.2333	867.357	.497	.968
RAP10	297.0333	874.309	.400	.968
RPP1	297.0000	879.793	.251	.968
RPP2	297.0667	872.478	.452	.968
RPP3	297.1667	861.730	.655	.967
RPP4	297.1333	870.533	.437	.968
RPP5	297.1000	868.852	.614	.967
RPP6	297.3333	874.161	.430	.968
RPP7	297.1667	877.109	.337	.968
RPP8	297.4000	864.110	.526	.968
RPP9	297.0000	872.345	.500	.968
RPP10	297.1333	865.568	.724	.967

Interpretation: $\alpha = .968$ therefore its reliability is interpreted as EXCELLENT

where $\alpha \geq 0.9$

Cronbach's Alpha SPSS RESULT

TEST-RETEST CORRELATION

Test of Stability

Pearson Product-Moment Correlation

Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
PRETEST	196.9333	22.17319	30
POSTTEST	202.0667	19.75005	30

Correlations

		PRETEST	POSTTEST
PRETEST	Pearson Correlation	1	.912**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	30	30
POSTTEST	Pearson Correlation	.912**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	30	30

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The table above shows the result of correlation between the respondents' pretest and post-test responses. With a p value of 0.912 and an r value of .000 or <0.01.

Interpretation

There is a significant relationship between the respondents' pretest and the posttest responses, therefore, the instrument's coefficient of stability is

RELIABLE.

CORRELATION

Result of Correlation using SPSS

IBM SPSS Statistics Viewer

File Edit View Data Transform Insert Format Analyze Direct Marketing Graphs Utilities Add-ons Window Help

Output Log Correlations

Correlations

CORRELATIONS
 /VARIABLES=PRETEST POSTTEST
 /PRINT=NOITAL1 NOSIG
 /STATISTICS=DESCRIPTIVES
 /MISSING=FAIRWISE.

Correlations

[DataSet1] C:\Users\DEPED-BCSRS-SAC-CBS\Downloads\TCC 2ND SEM 2022-2023\STAT THERIS 2024\LEARNING STYLE\LEARNING STYLE PILOT TESTING.sav

Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
PRETEST	196.8333	22.17319	30
POSTTEST	202.0667	19.75005	30

Correlations

		PRETEST	POSTTEST
PRETEST	Pearson Correlation	1	.912**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	30	30
POSTTEST	Pearson Correlation	.912**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	30	30

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Appendix D: Letter for Distribution of Questionnaire

REPUBLIC OF THE PHILIPPINES
PROVINCE OF BATANGAS
CITY GOVERNMENT OF TANAUAN
TANAUAN CITY COLLEGE

FEBRUARY 5, 2024

LOURDES T. BERMUDEZ, CESO V
Schools Division Superintendent
DepEd, Tanauan City Division

Ma'am;

We are bona fide students of Tanauan City College, taking up Bachelor of Technical-Vocational Teacher Education. We are currently conducting a study entitled, **"Divergent Learning Style and Reflective Learning Style of the Selected Junior High School Students"**

In this regards, we are seeking your permission to distribute the attached validated questionnaires to the Selected Junior High School Students of Ulango Integrated School for reliability testing and final data gathering.

Rest assured that the data to be obtained will be treated with utmost confidentiality and the result of the study will be submitted to the above-mentioned schools to contribute for its betterment.

Your permission will be of great contribution to the success of this undertaking. Thank you so much and more power.

Very truly yours,
Lianne A. Andaya
Cherry Grace M. Carandang
Mark Raven M. Carandang
Angelica Glodoviza
The Researchers

Noted:

Imelda P. Magpantay
IMELDA P. MAGPANTAY, LPT, PhD
Research Director
Jascelynn N. Olimpiada
JASCELYNN N. OLIMPIADA, LPT, PhD
Dean, School of Education/ VP for Academic Affairs
Marcial V. Goguanco, Jr.
MARCIAL V. GOGUANCO, JR.
Officer-in-Charge

REPUBLIC OF THE PHILIPPINES
 PROVINCE OF BATANGAS
 CITY GOVERNMENT OF TANAUAN
 TANAUAN CITY COLLEGE

February 12, 2024

NANCY B. MARALIT
 Ulango Integrated School
 Principal III

Madam:

We are bona fide students of Tanauan City College, taking up Bachelor of Technical-Vocational Teacher Education. We are currently conducting a study entitled "Divergent Learning Style and Reflective Learning Style of the Selected Junior High School Students".

In this regard, we are seeking your permission to distribute the attached questionnaire to the selected Junior High School students. Your permission will be of great contribution to the success of this undertaking. Rest assured that the answers will be treated with utmost confidentiality.

Thank you so much and more power.

Very truly yours,

ANDAYA, LIANNE A.

CARANDANG, CHERRY GRACE M.

CARANDANG, MARK RAVEN M.

GLODOVIZA, ANGELICA

Researchers

Noted:

MR. ROJANE F. BERNAS
 Thesis Adviser

Approved/Remarks:

NANCY/B. MARALIT
 Ulango Integrated School
 Principal III

Appendix E: Letter for Research Adviser, Grammarian, Statistician Form

Republic of the Philippines
Province of Batangas
CITY OF TANAUAN

TANAUAN CITY COLLEGE
TANAUAN City of Colors

E-mail: tanaucitycollege@gmail.com Tel. No.: (043) 702 – 6979; (043) 706 – 6961; (043) 706 – 3934

URL: <https://www.facebook.com/pages/Tanauan-City-College/554034167997845>

**RESEARCH ADVISER'S
FORM 1A**

Date: August 25, 2023

Program: Bachelor of Technical-Vocational Teacher Education

Major: Computer Hardware Servicing

Academic Year: 2023 - 2024

Semester: First Semester

This is to attest that I Rojane F. Bernas, LPT
Name of Research Study/ Policy Paper /Business Plan/ Capstone Project Adviser
have agreed and accepted to be the Adviser of the following students: Andaya, Lianne A., Carandang, Cherry Grace M., Carandang, Mark Raven M., Glodoviza, Angelica with the Research Study/ Policy Paper/Business Plan/Capstone Project entitled:
"Divergent Learning and Reflective Learning Style of Selected Junior High School Students"
Furthermore, I agree to set the schedule for advising and consultation to help the students and ensure the success of the study/project.

Rojane F. Bernas
ROJANE F. BERNAS, LPT. August 25, 2023
Conformed: Date

Noted by:
Shara May A. Logan
SHARA MAY A. LOGAN, LPT, MAED _____
Research Professor Date

Approved By:
Jascelynn N. Olimpiada
DR. JASCELYNN N. OLIMPIADA _____
Program Head Date

Please furnish copy the RDES0 and submit resume of the adviser

Republic of the Philippines
Province of Batangas
CITY OF TANAUAN

TANAUAN CITY COLLEGE
TANAUAN City of Colors

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URL: <https://www.facebook.com/pages/Tanauan-City-College/554034167997845>

**LANGUAGE EDITOR'S
FORM 1B**

Date: August 25, 2023

Program: Bachelor of Technical-Vocational Teacher Education

Major: Computer Hardware Servicing

Academic Year: 2023 - 2024

Semester: First Semester

This is to attest that I Venice S. Pagaspas, MAEd,
Name of Research Study/ Policy Paper/Business Plan/ Capstone Project Language Editor have agreed
and accepted to be the grammarian of the following students:
Andaya, Lianne A., Carandang, Cherry Grace M., Carandang, Mark Raven M.,
Glodoviza, Angelica with the Research Study/Policy Paper/Business Plan/Capstone
Project entitled:
"Divergent Learning and Reflective Learning Style of Selected Junior High School
Students"

Furthermore, I agree to set the schedule for checking the manuscript to help the
students and ensure the success of the study/project.

VENICE S. PAGASPAS, MAEd.
Conforme:

August 25, 2023
Date

Noted by:

SHARA MAY J. LOGAN, LPT, MAED
Research Professor

Date

Approved By:

DR. JASCELYNN N. OLIMPIADA
Program Head

Date

Please furnish copy the RDESO and submit resume of the language editor.

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Province of Batangas
CITY OF TANAUAN

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TANAUAN City of Colors

E-mail: tanauancitycollege@gmail.com Tel. No.: (043) 702 – 6979; (043) 706 – 6961; (043) 706 – 3934

URL: <https://www.facebook.com/pages/Tanauan-City-College/554034167997845>

**STATISTICIAN'S
FORM 1C**

Date: August 25, 2023

Program: Bachelor of Technical-Vocational Teacher Education

Major: Computer Hardware Servicing

Academic Year: 2023 - 2024

Semester: First Semester

This is to attest that I

Rojane F. Bernas, LPT.

Name of Research Study/ Policy Paper/Business Plan/ Capstone Project Statistician

have agreed and accepted to be the statistician of the following students: Andaya, Lianne A., Carandang, Cherry Grace M., Carandang, Mark Raven M., Glodoviza, Angelica with the Research/Business Plan/Capstone Project entitled:

“Divergent Learning and Reflective Learning Style of Selected Junior High School Students”

Furthermore, I agree to set the schedule to assist the student-researchers to determine appropriate statistical procedures for the analysis of research data and ensure the success of the study/project.

ROJANE F. BERNAS, LPT.

Conforme:

August 25, 2023

Date

Noted by:

SHARA MAY J. LOGAN, LPT, MAED

Research Professor

_____ Date

Approved By:

DR. JASCERYNN N. OLIMPIADA

Program Head

_____ Date

Please furnish copy the RDESO and submit resume of the statistician.

Appendix F: Distribution Tables, Computation of Mean

Table A
Respondents of the Study

Grade Level	Total Population	Sample Size	Percentage
Grade 7	53	33	23%
Grade 8	59	38	26%
Grade 9	49	32	22%
Grade 10	66	42	29%
Total	227	145	100%

Table B
Interpretation of Mean Ranges

Numerical Value	Mean Range	Interpretations
4	4.00 - 3.25	Strongly Agree
3	3.24 - 2.50	Agree
2	2.49 - 1.75	Disagree
1	1.74 - 1.00	Strongly Disagree

Table 1.1

Students' Evaluation of the Divergent Learning Style in terms of Cognitive.

Indicators	M	SD	VI
As a student, I...			
1. am naturally inclined to generate multiple ideas, even if they seem unconventional or impractical.	3.12	0.71	Agree
2. am consciously evaluate multiple alternatives and select the most appropriate one after careful consideration.	3.17	0.73	Agree
3. am open to considering new ideas and perspectives, even if they challenge my existing beliefs.	3.26	0.70	Strongly agree
4. find myself seeking out diverse viewpoints to enrich my understanding and problem-solving abilities.	3.14	0.76	Agree
5. suggest multiple solutions to problems, considering both conventional and unconventional approaches.	3.28	0.68	Strongly Agree
6. am comfortable with ambiguity and uncertainty, embracing the open-ended nature of creative thinking.	3.14	0.77	Agree
7. find it exciting to generate innovative ideas and explore uncharted territories in my thinking.	3.12	0.77	Agree
8. usually question the ways of thinking to come up with new and creative ideas.	3.19	0.71	Agree
9. extend the power of divergent thinking in generating novel solutions and fostering creativity.	3.14	0.71	Agree
10. am committed to develop my divergent thinking skills to enhance my problem-solving and innovative potential.	3.31	0.70	Strongly Agree
GENERAL WEIGHTED MEAN	3.19	0.03	Agree

M-(mean), *VI*-(verbal interpretation), *SD*-(standard deviation), 4.00-3.25- (strongly agree), 3.24-2.50- (agree), 2.49-1.75 -(disagree), 1.74-1.00- (strongly disagree)

Table 1.2

Students' Evaluation of the Divergent Learning Style in terms of Affective.

Indicators	M	SD	VI
As a student, I...			
1. feel energized and excited when I am encouraged to generate multiple ideas and explore different possibilities.	3.32	0.69	Strongly Agree
2. find immense satisfaction in participating in brainstorming sessions where I feel free to express my unique ideas, not having any burden by the fear of criticism or judgment.	3.26	0.63	Strongly Agree
3. feel a sense of accomplishment when I come up with innovative solutions or unconventional approaches to problems.	3.30	0.66	Strongly Agree
4. find myself developing a more positive attitude towards risk-taking and embracing uncertainty in the learning process.	3.33	0.76	Strongly Agree
5. appreciate the opportunity to collaborate with others as I can conceptualize the connection from different perspectives.	3.21	0.68	Agree
6. feel a sense of belongingness when I participate in divergent thinking activities in the classroom.	3.20	0.71	Agree
7. am more likely to engage with the learning material when I am encouraged to explore different perspectives and approaches.	3.28	0.67	Strongly Agree
8. find myself developing a stronger sense of creativity and innovation as I engage in divergent thinking activities.	3.26	0.67	Strongly Agree
9. appreciate the value of divergent thinking in fostering open-mindedness and adaptability to change.	3.28	0.68	Strongly Agree
10. am committed to develop my divergent thinking skills to enhance my problem-solving and creative potential.	3.32	0.67	Agree
General Weighted Mean	3.27	0.03	Strongly Agree

M-(mean), *VI*-(verbal interpretation), *SD*-(standard deviation), 4.00-3.25- (strongly agree), 3.24-2.50- (agree), 2.49-1.75 -(disagree), 1.74-1.00- (strongly disagree)

Table 1.3
Students' Evaluation of the Divergent Learning Style
in terms of Psychomotor

Indicators	M	SD	VI
As a student, I...			
1. am able to generate multiple strategies and approaches to solving physical tasks.	3.32	0.67	Strongly Agree
2. try new things and experiment with different materials and techniques during hands-on activities.	3.33	0.71	Strongly Agree
3. participate in hands-on activities, and this challenged me to think outside the box.	3.24	0.66	Agree
4. can effectively express my ideas creatively through writing, drawing, or other mediums.	3.20	0.76	Agree
5. can collaborate with others using physical means to generate and develop creative ideas.	3.47	0.66	Agree
6. like to practice until I can do things smoothly and consistently.	3.32	0.72	Strongly Agree
7. enjoy refining my skills and achieving perfect control.	3.34	0.68	Strongly Agree
8. can create something entirely new and original.	3.22	0.76	Agree
9. learn by watching and imitating exactly what is being demonstrated.	3.20	0.75	Agree
10. can review in different ways, such as by creating flashcards, doing peer study, and creating scenarios.	3.30	0.72	Agree
General Weighted Mean	3.29	0.35	Strongly Agree

M-(mean), *VI*-(verbal interpretation), *SD*-(standard deviation), 4.00-3.25- (strongly agree), 3.24-2.50- (agree), 2.49-1.75 -(disagree), 1.74-1.00- (strongly disagree)

Table 2.1
Students' Evaluation of the Reflective Learning Style in terms of Cognitive.

Indicators	M	SD	VI
As a student, I...			
1. often think about how new information is somewhat connected to what I already know.	3.13	.59	Agree
2. find myself analyzing information carefully to ensure I thoroughly grasp it.	3.23	.70	Agree
3. regularly evaluate the pros and cons of different ideas before making a decision.	3.14	.80	Agree
4. am inclined to reflect on my learning experiences to gain deeper insights.	3.08	.70	Agree
5. connect new information to my personal experiences and beliefs to enhance understanding.	3.28	.68	Strongly Agree
6. am drawn to consider the implications of new information in real-world scenarios.	3.03	.74	Agree
7. find myself questioning assumptions and seeking multiple perspectives to gain a comprehensive understanding.	3.09	.70	Agree
8. am inclined to revisit and revise my understanding of concepts based on new information and reflections.	3.10	.70	Agree
9. understand the process of self-reflection to enhance my learning and personal growth.	3.24	.70	Agree
10. am committed to continuous learning and seeking opportunities to broaden my knowledge and understanding.	3.25	.72	Strongly Agree
GENERAL WEIGHTED MEAN	3.16	.05	Agree

Table 2.2
Students' Evaluation of the Divergent Learning Style in terms of Affective.

Indicators	M	SD	VI
As a student, I...			
1. feel personally motivated to understand the concepts being taught in class.	3.32	.63	Strongly Agree
2. experience a sense of satisfaction when I connect new information to my own experiences and beliefs.	3.21	.69	Agree
3. find myself developing a deeper appreciation for the subject matter as I engage in reflective thinking.	3.11	.77	Agree
4. am more likely to retain information when I take the time to reflect on it and make it meaningful to me.	3.14	.73	Agree
5. feel a sense of empowerment when I use reflective thinking to enhance my understanding and personal growth.	3.16	.68	Agree
6. am more confident in my ability to apply new information to real-world situations after engaging in reflective thinking.	3.10	.65	Agree
7. find myself developing a stronger sense of self-awareness as I reflect on my learning experiences.	3.52	.39	Strongly Agree
8. am more open to consider multiple perspectives as I engage in reflective thinking.	3.20	.65	Agree
9. appreciate the opportunity to express my personal thoughts and reflections in the classroom.	3.13	.76	Agree
10. feel valued and respected when my reflective contributions are acknowledged and encouraged in the learning environment.	3.44	.61	Strongly Agree
General Weighted Mean	3.23	.10	Agree

M-(mean), *VI*-(verbal interpretation), *SD*-(standard deviation), 4.00-3.25- (strongly agree), 3.24-2.50- (agree), 2.49-1.75 - (disagree), 1.74-1.00- (strongly disagree)

Table 2.3
Students' Evaluation of the Reflective Learning Style in terms of Psychomotor.

Indicators	M	SD	VI
As a student, I...			
1. can apply the concepts learned in class to perform physical tasks effectively.	3.27	.64	Strongly Agree
2. try to identify the key concepts and principles I learn during hands-on activities.	3.22	.65	Agree
3. share my reflections with others to gain different perspectives on my learning.	3.17	.76	Agree
4. can effectively use what I have learned from my experiences through writing, drawing, and other mediums.	3.05	.74	Agree
5. can think back on the lessons I have learned from my experiences to come up with a better idea, solution, or answer.	3.24	.67	Agree
6. can do things smoothly and consistently through analyzing my performance and identifying areas for improvement.	3.14	.65	Agree
7. reflect on my process and explore ways to refine my skills and achieve perfect control.	3.16	.75	Agree
8. can create something unique and original by reflecting and adapting existing ideas.	3.13	.67	Agree
9. learn effectively by observing others, but I prioritize internalizing the skills and adapting them to my strengths and learning preferences.	3.40	.58	Strongly Agree
10. can review by reflecting on the concepts that have been taught to the class.	3.20	.68	Agree
General Weighted Mean	3.20	.05	Agree

M-(mean), *VI*-(verbal interpretation), *SD*-(standard deviation), 4.00-3.25- (strongly agree), 3.24-2.50- (agree), 2.49-1.75 - (disagree), 1.74-1.00- (strongly disagree)

Table 3
Significant Differences between Divergent and Reflective Learning Style

Variables	Mean	Std. Deviation	T	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Decision (H₀)	Interpretation
Divergent and Reflective Learning Styles	0.05	0.29	2.23	14	0.027	Reject H ₀	Significant

Appendix G: Computation of Significant Difference

SOP3: Significant Difference.

Variables	Mean	Std. Deviation	T	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Decision (H ₀)	Interpretation
Divergent and Reflective Learning Styles	0.05	0.29	2.23	144	0.027	Reject H ₀	Significant

The mean difference between Divergent and Reflective Learning Styles is significant at $\alpha = 0.05$. This is because 'Sig. (2-tailed)' or $p < 0.05$. Divergent and Reflective Learning Styles do differ statistically significant, $t(144) = 2.23$, $p = 0.027$.

CURRICULUM VITAE

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PERSONAL INFORMATION

Date of Birth	May 23,2002
Place of Birth	Brgy. Balele, Tanauan City, Batangas
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Father's Name	Ricky G. Carandang
Mother's Name	Adela M. Carandang

EDUCATION BACKGROUND

Senior High School	Balele Integrated Highschool S.Y. 2018-2020
Secondary	Balele Integrated Highschool S.Y. 2017-2013
Primary	Balele Elementary School S.Y. 2008-2013

CHARACTER REFERENCE

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 Brgy Captain
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I hereby certify that the above mentioned is true and correct.

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EDUCATION

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Elementary	Bernardo Lirio Memorial Central School S.Y. 2013 - 2014

CHARACTER REFERENCE

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City Mayor
 Tanauan City, Batangas

I hereby that the above mentioned is true and correct.

ANGELICA GLODOVIZA

Applicants' Signature
